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Organic geochemical investigation of Cretaceous source rocks with varying thermal maturity levels in the East Andes (Boyacá, Colombia)

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Abstract:	<p>This study encompasses a geochemical investigation of Cretaceous source rocks from the Eastern Cordillera (Colombia). This basin represents an interesting area for geochemical studies due to its abundance of organic matter-rich levels, some of which exhibit mild to extremely high thermal maturities, enabling discussion on long-term carbon sinks. This research work focuses on the study of organic-rich shaly sediments of Berremian to Campanian age from seven (7) outcrop locations in two areas of the Boyacá Department. A set of seventy (70) rock samples have been analysed using several organic geochemical techniques and have shown to cover thermal maturity ranges from the early oil window to the metagenesis stage (measured reflectance values from 0.6% to 2.1%). The OAE2 event was identified based on a 2.5‰ to 3‰ carbon isotopic excursion in the distal Guaguaquí Group from the section along the Guaguaquí River. Maturity was not found to correlate with depositional burial depths in the so-called distal study area, suggesting that other tectonic events may have played an important role in the genetic history of hydrocarbons particularly in this part of the Boyacá Department. During the mid-to late Cretaceous times, the two study areas consisted of a marine margin with a terrestrial input from the east, which is reflected in a higher terrestrial character of sediments in the eastern foothills ($V/Ni < 0.7$) compared to the others. Finally, fluorene- and diamondoid-based components were used for enhancing the characterization of the mid-to late Cretaceous organic matter in terms of source in the study sub-region (three-fluorenes and dimethyl-/trimethyl-adamantanes ratios above or below 0.25 and 0.85).</p>
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Opposed Reviewers:	
Response to Reviewers:	

Dear Dr. Montes:

I am submitting the last modified version of the manuscript (SAMES-D-23-00745) entitled “*Organic geochemical investigation of Cretaceous source rocks with varying thermal maturity levels in the East Andes (Boyacá, Colombia)*” for your considerations in order to be published in *J. South Am. Earth Sci.* The authors appreciate your comments and the additional clarification provided, which has helped us improve the original manuscript.

Attached you can find highlights, revised copies (clean and with track changes) and detail response to reviewers.

Yours sincerely,

Dra. Erica Lorenzo

Dear Dr. Montes:

As shown below, your comments have been addressed. All minor changes have been also followed in the revised manuscript.

Comments

Reply and changes

<p><i>First, a table with the coordinates (decimal degrees, 3 digits) of all samples reported must be included (or the coordinates of all the boreholes).</i></p>	<p>As suggested by the editor, the coordinates of sampling sites and the C3n3ndor-1 borehole have been added to the caption of Figure 1. Figure 1 has also been improved considering the decimal coordinates on Google Earth.</p>
<p><i>Second, the axes in all graphs need to be specified, be it intensity of absorbance (in units of mAU, or milli-Absorbance Units) or time</i></p>	<p>The axes in several graphs have been specified in the figure captions, now it is clearly stated which item corresponds to each axis. Noteworthy is that the authors have aimed to comply with the editor's requirement; however, it is common in the scientific literature associated with petroleum geochemistry not to specify the axes in the case of mass chromatograms.</p>
<p><i>Third, the stratigraphic nomenclature should at least acknowledge possible correlations to more widely known units in the region, as the reviewers point out.</i></p>	<p>Regarding stratigraphic nomenclature of the units in the distal area, an in-depth study was conducted in the literature reported for such area and, consequently, some conclusions were reached. Thus, the reference (Villamil, 1998) did not correspond to the information being provided and it was replaced by the correct reference (Rodríguez and Ulloa, 1994). In fact, sampling points in the distal area are located near Puerto Boyac3a city in a zone limited by latitudes from about 53n30' N to 53n50' N and longitudes from about 743n00' W to 743n20' W. In this regard, the stratigraphic nomenclature had some errors that have been solved both in the text and in Fig. 2; in detail, Guaguaqu3 and Olini units were initially considered as formations, when they both were defined as groups by Rodr3guez and Ulloa (1994). Finally, it should</p>

	<p>be emphasized that neither my co-authors nor I have found other chronostratigraphic column definition different from the one defined by Rodriguez and Ulloa in the explanatory report of sheet 169 of Puerto Boyacá in Colombia. If this is not the case, I must strongly request you or Reviewer 2 to provide us with the appropriate reference instead of Rodriguez and Ulloa (1994).</p>
<p><i>Fourth, the abstract needs to contain more of the quantitative data you derive from your study, while remaining short.</i></p>	<p>Quantitative data on vitrinite reflectance, carbon isotopes, and vanadium-nickel ratio have been included in the abstract.</p>
<p><i>The newly included paragraphs need to be revised by a fully proficient English speaker.</i></p>	<p>English has been thoroughly reviewed according to suggestion.</p>

Note: Please, be aware of changes (**underlined**) in the manuscript.

Enclosed you will find the text, figures and tables.

Yours sincerely, Dra. Erica Lorenzo

The Eastern Cordillera is one of the most prolific petroliferous regions of Colombia

Organic geochemistry of Cretaceous strata in the foothills of the East Andes (Boyacá)

Comparing the depositional settings and maturities of study source types in Boyacá

Using aromatic hydrocarbons and diamondoid-based proxies for source characterization

Assessing novel molecular geochemical parameters at very high thermal maturity levels

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Organic geochemical investigation of Cretaceous source rocks with varying thermal maturity levels in the East Andes (Boyacá, Colombia)

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Abstract: This study encompasses a geochemical investigation of Cretaceous source rocks from the Eastern Cordillera (Colombia). This basin represents an interesting area for geochemical studies due to its abundance of organic matter-rich levels, some of which exhibit mild to extremely high thermal maturities, enabling discussion on long-term carbon sinks. This research work focuses on the study of organic-rich shaly sediments of Berremian to Campanian age from seven (7) outcrop locations in two areas of the Boyacá Department. A set of seventy (70) rock samples have been analysed using several organic geochemical techniques and have shown to cover thermal maturity ranges from the early oil window to the metagenesis stage (measured reflectance values from 0.6% to 2.1%). The OAE2 event was identified based on a 2.5‰ to 3‰ carbon isotopic excursion in the distal Guaguaquí Group from the section along the Guaguaquí River. Maturity was not found to correlate with depositional burial depths in the so-called distal study area, suggesting that other tectonic events may have played an important role in the genetic history of hydrocarbons particularly in this part of the Boyacá Department. During the mid-to late Cretaceous times, the two study areas consisted of a marine margin with a terrestrial input from the east, which is reflected in a higher terrestrial character of sediments in the eastern foothills ($V/Ni < 0.7$) compared to the others. Finally, fluorene- and diamondoid-based components were used for enhancing the characterization of the mid-to late Cretaceous organic matter in terms of source in the study sub-region (three-fluorenes and dimethyl-/trimethyl-adamantanes ratios above or below 0.25 and 0.85).

Keywords: Cretaceous source rocks, Eastern Cordillera, thermal maturity, precursor organic matter, diamondoids

1. Introduction

The Eastern Cordillera, of ca. 60.000 km², has constituted one of the most prolific petroleum producing regions of Colombia and northern South America along with the Llanos and Middle and Upper Magdalena Basins (e.g., Sánchez et al., 2015). Commercial oil exploration in the area started in the mid-1920s, motivated by the abundant number of oil seeps found in the basin (Ramón et al., 2001; Aguilera et al., 2010). Within the region, multiple source rock levels are identified, of pre-Cretaceous to Tertiary age, which are mainly located in the Magdalena and Eastern Cordillera (e.g. Palmer and Russell, 1988). Among these, it is remarkable the number of lower to upper Cretaceous organic-rich levels exhibiting fair to excellent generation potential.

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35 During the Cretaceous period, organic-rich layers were deposited across the territory now
36 recognized as Colombia, forming a foreland basin in the latest Cretaceous (Cooper et al., 1995;
37 Villamil, 1998). The regional configuration resulted in a wide variety of paleo-depositional
38 environments, leading to lateral and vertical changes in organic source and richness (Blanco-
39 Velandia, 2012). Subsequently, extensive sediment thicknesses and volcanism associated with
40 compressional tectonics led to high thermal maturities of the organic-rich sediments (Mora et al.,
41 2010). Based on these assessments, the Colombian East Andes cover an interesting region for
42 petroleum geochemical studies, allowing for the evaluation of organic geochemistry in shaly facies
43 representing different levels of thermal maturity and types of organic matter.

44 In the Boyacá sub-region (Fig. 1), gas- and oil-prone Cretaceous shale-rich intervals have been
45 identified as probable source rocks of fair to excellent generative potential in the eastern and
46 western foothills of the East-Andean Cordillera, respectively: the Fomeque (TOC > 1%) and Paja
47 (TOC below 3% on average) formations in the late Barremian and Aptian times (Gaona-Narváez et
48 al., 2013), the Une (TOC in the 2-8% range) and Guaguaquí (TOC > 2%) facies deposited in the
49 Albian-Cenomanian period (Zavala et al., 2009); Turonian-Santonian source rocks (TOC > 4%) of
50 the Chipaque Formation and Olini Group (Blanco-Velandia, 2012), and infrequent organic-rich
51 strata of the Campanian Guadalupe and Cordoba formations (Palmer and Russell, 1988; Moretti et
52 al., 2009). Among the Barremian to Campanian stratigraphic units under study, the Chipaque
53 formation and Guaguaquí group have been reported to contain locally good source potential in the
54 Eastern Cordillera (Ramón et al., 2001). They both were deposited during periods of sea level
55 highstand, partly coinciding with the latest Cenomanian-early Turonian oceanic anoxic event
56 (OEA2); therefore, some of the highest organic carbon contents in these facies are associated with
57 OAE2 (Villamil, 1998).

58

59 Newly sampled lower to upper Cretaceous organic-rich rocks collected from the western and
60 eastern foothills of the Eastern Cordillera (here referred as distal and proximal areas corresponding

61 to different paleo-depositional environments as stated by Guerrero and Sarmiento in 1996) are the
62 target study. Until now no studies have been conducted on Cretaceous shales of different maturity
63 levels and proximal to distal palaeo-settings in Boyacá province for recognizing reliable parameters
64 based on aromatic biomarkers and diamondoid-related ratios for source characterization in highly
65 mature sediments. In this regard, the present research work is of interest to investigate
66 lateral/vertical variations in the paleo-depositional conditions of Cretaceous organic-rich strata
67 within the study area in the Colombian Eastern Andes and, simultaneously, to assess molecular
68 geochemical parameters at varying (particularly high) thermal maturation levels after comparing
69 samples from two areas associated with distal and proximal settings at similar levels of maturity.

70

71 This work focuses on the organic geochemical study of Cretaceous sediments from the foothills of
72 the East-Andean Cordillera. The two studied areas are located in the Boyacá Department
73 (Colombia), roughly 85 km north and 55 km northeast of Bogotá city, respectively (Fig. 1). The
74 aims of the present study are: (i) enhancing the characterization of thermal maturities, sources, and
75 depositional settings of the Cretaceous sediments in the Boyacá sub-region; (ii) comparing the
76 characteristics of different age-equivalent rock intervals between Barremian and Campanian times
77 corresponding to the two areas under study in the Boyacá Department; and (iii) integrating the
78 source and paleo-environment information obtained into its geological/stratigraphic context. All this
79 information will be useful to improve the models of the paleo-deposition of the study Cretaceous
80 organic-rich sediments in the study sub-region and their petroleum generation history.

81

82 **2. Geological background**

83 The Eastern Cordillera constitutes the eastern mountain range of the Colombian Andes (Fig. 1). Its
84 structure consists of a double-verging fold-and-thrust belt ranging NE-SW of mostly Mesozoic
85 marine sediments placed over a Precambrian-Paleozoic polydeformed basement. The boundaries of
86 the Eastern Cordillera are defined by igneous/metamorphic rocks from the Santander Massif in the

87 north, the Algeciras-Garzón fault system in the south, and the Middle/Upper Magdalena and the
88 Llanos foreland basins in the west and east, respectively (e.g., Cooper et al., 1995, Restrepo-Pace et
89 al., 2004).

90

91 The genesis of the Colombian Andes has its initiation in the subduction of the Caribbean and Nazca
92 oceanic plates beneath the South America continental lithospheric plate (Taboada et al., 2000). The
93 geological history of the Eastern Cordillera (from the Late Jurassic to today) comprises four stages
94 (Cooper et al., 1995; Moreno-López and Escalona, 2015): (i) during Early Cretaceous times (up to
95 Hauterivian), the terminal rifting phase, rift basins progressively developed inland due to the
96 separation of the North and South America plates (NW-SE stress) and progressive opening of the
97 Caribbean Sea; (ii) a period of thermal post-rift subsidence and incipient transgression occurred
98 from Hauterivian to early Albian in a back-arc setting, where normal faults still controlled the
99 turbiditic-dominated deposition during this stage; (iii) the intensification of the transgressive
100 episode, coinciding with an Albian-late Coniacian period of low tectonic activity, which resulted in
101 the development of a vast regional retro-arc basin in which the deposition of the main Cretaceous
102 source rocks took place; (iv) a regional sea-level fall occurred, coinciding with the uplift of the
103 ancestral Central Cordillera (Santonian-Maastrichtian), which led to the beginning of a regressive
104 sequence; and (v) lastly, as convergence rates increased, compressional tectonics led progressively
105 to the inversion of Mesozoic faults, uplift of the Eastern Cordillera and partitioning of the regional
106 foreland depression into the Magdalena and Llanos foreland basins.

107

108 Throughout almost the entire Cretaceous period, the Eastern Cordillera consisted of a sedimentary
109 basin whose configuration and sediment-type accumulation evolved roughly from being terrigenous
110 synrift-dominated (Berriasian-Valanginian) to regionally spread marine-dominated (late Aptian-
111 Maastrichtian; Villamil, 1998). Maximum palaeo-water depths in the Boyaca sub-region were
112 reached around the Cenomanian-Turonian boundary, when the main Cretaceous source rocks were

113 deposited in a marine margin which extended from Peru to Venezuela (Villamil, 1998). The main
114 continental supply came from the Guyana Shield (i.e. from the east; that is why our eastern study
115 area is called proximal) and greater accommodation space was created towards the west and north.

116

117 In the so-called distal area or western foothills (Fig. 1), the Cretaceous covers ages from Late
118 Valanginian to Campanian-Maastrichtian (Fig. 2) and tends to be folded in wide structures and
119 faulted (inverse SW-NE faults dipping SE; Rangel et al., 1996). The Paja Formation consists of
120 mostly black calcareous and highly micaceous shales (Gaona-Narváez et al., 2013), and it is
121 traditionally correlated with the Fomeque Formation from the eastern flank of the Eastern
122 Cordillera (Moretti et al., 2009). The Puerto Romero Formation comprises dark grey limestones
123 alternating with black claystones (Rodríguez and Ulloa, 1994). The locally named Guaguaquí
124 Group represents the sedimentation of black micaceous shales with limestones, siltstones, and
125 cherts (Mahoney, 2018). The Olini Group is characterized as a two-package succession of
126 calcareous siltstones with alternating siliceous siltstones and cherts known as Lidita Superior and
127 Lidita Inferior), which are intercalated with a package of grey mudstones. Finally, the Cordoba
128 Formation consists mostly of dark grey calcareous siltstones (Rodríguez and Ulloa, 1994). In the
129 proximal area or eastern foothills, the Cretaceous is almost fully represented (Berriasian to
130 Maastrichtian; Fig. 2), with the youngest sediments outcropping towards the northwest. Within this
131 area, in the southern part the Cretaceous tends to be folded in symmetric and wide structures, whilst
132 towards the north, the tectonic complexity increases, and the structures are narrower. The Macanal
133 Formation mostly consists of calcareous shales with intercalated sandstone levels and depicts
134 thermal maturity in the metagenesis stage (Mahoney, 2018). The Las Juntas Formation is defined by
135 two sequences of quartz sandstones with interbedded black shales intercalated by a package of
136 black shales (Rodríguez and Ulloa, 1994). The Fomeque unit consists of grey to black shales
137 alternating with limestone, sandstone, and cherts (Moretti et al., 2009). The Une Formation
138 comprises quartz arenites interbedded with thin layers of mudstones, siltstones, and marly shales

139 (Zavala et al., 2009). The Chipaque unit is described as an intercalation of black shales and
140 siltstones with siliceous sands and scarce limestones (García et al., 2025). The overlying Guadalupe
141 Formation consists of quartz arenites and greywackes alternating with scarce levels of coaly shales
142 and cherts (Sarmiento, 2001). Lastly, the Guaduas unit comprises mainly shales with sandstone and
143 coal beds (Valenzuela, 2002).

144

145 **3. Samples and methods**

146 3.1. Samples pre-selected

147 A set of seventy (70) pre-selected rock samples were collected from seven outcrop locations (Fig.
148 1), which cover most of the Cretaceous in the foothills of the East-Andean Cordillera of Colombia.
149 These are distributed as follows: in the proximal area (eastern foothills), 13, 12, 5 and 5
150 representative samples were collected from the sections near the Chitamena River (PE), between the
151 Hatalaguna River and the village of Llano de Alarcón (H), along the west (WL) and east (EL) sides
152 of the Lengupá River; in the distal area (western foothills), 2, 23, and 10 samples were also
153 collected from the sections near the Minero River and San Pablo de Borbur village (M), between
154 the Guaguaquí River and Puerto Romero city (G), and close to the La Zambra Reserve (Z). This
155 latter section and the previous one are subdivided in lower/upper parts and in four segments named
156 s1, s2, s3, and s4, respectively. The sampling interval of each section or sub-section under study in
157 the respective stratigraphic record is shown in Figure 2. The lithological descriptions of samples are
158 compiled in the Table 1. For comparison purposes, data on two cores, one of them from the
159 Guadalupe unit (3360-3364 m depth) and the other from the Une Formation (4188-4190 m depth),
160 of the El Cóndor-1 borehole (see Fig. 1; Cuñado, 2012), located in the eastern foothills, have been
161 also considered. Experimental work was performed in the facilities of the Geological Research
162 Center of Guayaquil, except isotopic analyses at the Andalusian Earth Sciences Institute (Granada).

163

164 3.2. Analytical methods

165 3.2.1. Screening analyses

166 First, aliquots of samples (approximately 5 g each) were dried at 40 °C for 24 hours, pulverized in
167 an agate mortar and treated with a 1 M HCl solution to remove the carbonates and sulfates (Verardo
168 et al., 1990). Later, 60 mg aliquots of each powdered rock were run in a LECO CS-300 instrument
169 for TOC contents. Vitrinite reflectance (VR) analyses were performed on some aliquots of ca. 5 g of
170 dried rock sample (40°C for 48 hours). Rock-Eval pyrolysis of samples was done using a Delsi II
171 Rock Eval equipment. These latter measurements were performed using 60 mg aliquots of the
172 carbonate-free powdered rock, and the basic methodology was used (Espitalié et al., 1977). About
173 120 g of selected rock samples were pulverized after being rinsed with petroleum ether, and then
174 extraction of the bitumen was performed on a Soxhlet apparatus (93:7 v/v of dichloromethane and
175 methanol) for 48 h. About 1.5 g of activated copper was added to the mixture of solvents to capture
176 tiny residues of elemental sulphur during the extraction of the rock. Bitumen was concentrated
177 using a rotavapor instrument to 10 ml (temperature <20 °C) and a small homogenized aliquot
178 (0.6 ml) was taken for extractable organic matter (EOM) measurements. Lastly, for determining
179 maturity levels of the Minero River samples, TAI (thermal alteration index; Staplin, 1977) was also
180 determined in amorphous organic matter (Peters et al., 1977).

181

182 3.2.2. Bitumen analyses

183 Previous separation of asphaltenes by using *n*-heptane in a 1:40 v/v ratio, saturated and aromatic
184 hydrocarbons were then fractionated by liquid chromatography (De la Cruz et al., 1997). The
185 aliphatic hydrocarbons were eluted with *n*-hexane, the aromatics with toluene, and the resins with
186 toluene/methanol (70:30 v/v) using a column filled with silica-alumina. Both fractions were
187 analysed by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), in full scan and selected ion
188 monitoring (SIM) modes. Before performing GC-MS analyses of lower diamondoids on samples,
189 saturate fractions of representative rock extracts were treated with ZSM-5 zeolite to remove *n*-
190 alkanes (He et al., 2012). An Agilent 7890A gas chromatogram with a HP-5 fused silica capillary

191 column (30 m length; 0.25 mm ID, 0.25 μm film thickness), coupled to a 5975C mass spectrometer
192 was used. Samples (1 μl) were auto injected with splitless injection. Helium was used as a carrier
193 gas, operated at a constant flow of 1 ml/min. The oven was programmed from an initial temperature
194 of 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (3 min initial hold time), to a final temperature of 310 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, at a constant rate of 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$
195 (20 min final hold time). The mass spectrometer was operated in electron ionization mode (EI) at
196 70 eV. Data processing was done with Chemstation software. On an aliquot of each bitumen
197 extract, sulfur content and V/Ni ratio were determined using an energy dispersive X-ray Panalytical
198 Axios spectrometer and a Perkin Elmer Optima 3000 DV inductively coupled plasma optical
199 emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) system, respectively.

200

201 3.2.2. Isotopic analysis

202 After kerogen isolation of ca. 3g of pulverized rock samples following the procedure designed by
203 Durand and Nicaise (1980), kerogen concentrates were placed in precombusted tin cups and
204 oxidized (combustion furnace held at 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) in a Thermo Finnigan 1112 Elemental Analyzer
205 interfaced to a Finnigan MAT Delta V Mass Spectrometer for determination of C isotopic data.
206 Some of the samples were run in duplicates and standard deviations were below 0.12. The $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$
207 data is reported as $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values, relative to the Vienna Peedee Belemnite (VPDB). Standards used
208 were IA-001 (wheat flour), IA-R005 (beet sugar), and IA-R006 (cane sugar), which were evenly
209 intercalated between the samples.

210

211 4. Results

212 4.1. Thermal maturity characterization

213 4.1.1. Measured vitrinite reflectance and bitumen yield.

214 A wide range of T_{max} values is represented in the samples analyzed, from 427 to 603 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Table 2).
215 Among the stratigraphic columns, Chitamena River section averages the lowest T_{max} value (434 $^{\circ}\text{C}$),
216 followed by Guaguaquí River-s1 (454 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), and other five (Guaguaquí River-s2 and -s4, Hatalaguna

217 River, as well as Upper and Lower La Zambra Reserve) average T_{max} in the range 460-470 °C.
218 Further, Guaguaquí River-s3, as well as west and east Lengupá River samples have T_{max} values
219 around or exceeding 500°C. Lastly, Minero River samples correspond to residual S2 yields below
220 0.1 mg HC/g rock which are interpreted as leading to an inaccurate T_{max} of 493°C (Peters, 1986).
221
222 Measured vitrinite reflectance (VR) values also vary among a subset of the studied samples from
223 0.57% to 2.07% (Table 2). Chitamena River section (Chipaque unit) shows the lowest average
224 (0.59%); followed by Hatalaguna River (0.96%), Guaguaquí River-s1 (0.93%), Lower and Upper
225 La Zambra Reserve (1.05 and 1.07%, respectively), Guaguaquí River-s4 (1.27%) and -s2 (1.33%);
226 Guaguaquí River-s3 has an average VR value of 1.69%, while west and east Lengupá River
227 sections (Fomeque Formation), respectively, average 1.74% and 1.88%. Samples from the Minero
228 River section (Paja Formation) have an average measured VR value of 2.03%.
229
230 Significant amounts of EOM (averaging values > 4 mg HC/g rock) are obtained in Upper La
231 Zambra Reserve section (Córdoba Formation), Guaguaquí River-s1 and -s2 (Guaguaquí unit), as
232 well as -s4 (Lower Olini Group) and some of the Hatalaguna River samples (Table 2). The
233 Chitamena River samples have EOM values averaging 3.43 mg HC/g rock. The samples from
234 Lower La Zambra Reserve (Lower Olini Group), west Lengupá River, Guaguaquí River-s3
235 (Guaguaquí unit), and some of the Hatalaguna River section (Chipaque unit) exhibit lower EOM
236 abundances compared to the latter ones (Table 2). The amount of EOM is expected to increase in
237 early to peak oil source rocks and to decrease after the late oil window (Miles, 1989). Lastly,
238 several samples yielded very little EOM or bitumen below the detection limit of the scale and are
239 indicated in Table 2 as <0.15 mg HC/g rock. These correspond to all the analysed east Lengupá
240 River and Minero River samples, as well as some from west Lengupá River. In these three sections,
241 TOC contents are not negligible (Table 1). Thus, the low bitumen amounts are here interpreted as a
242 sign of thermal over-maturation rather than poor organic matter contents.

243

244 4.1.2. Molecular maturity parameters

245 Molecular maturity indicators (Table 3), including biomarkers, diamondoid-based, and aromatic
246 parameters, have been investigated in the study sediments to obtain additional maturity assessment.
247 Note that some of these parameters could not be calculated in some samples (e.g. Minero River
248 section), as these components were absent or not well-resolved in the saturated or aromatic
249 fractions. Also, even though in some other cases saturated, aromatic, and diamondoid compounds
250 could be resolved, certain parameters were not suitable for assessing thermal maturation because
251 their levels of thermal maturity do not correspond to their application range (e.g. some aromatic
252 hydrocarbons in Chitamena River or diamondoids in Minero River, west and east Lengupá River
253 sections).

254

255 Excluding a few marginally mature samples from the top of the Chitamena River section, with
256 values of $22S\% < 57\%$ (see Table 2), all the samples exhibit homohopane isomerization values
257 ($\%22S$) in the 0.57-0.62 range, indicating that the corresponding equilibrium stage has been reached
258 (Peters et al., 2005), and these rocks have entered the oil window. In Chitamena River, sterane
259 isomerization ratios ($\%20S$ and $\%\beta\beta$) averaging 40% and 32%, respectively, would indicate
260 maturity levels at the beginning of the oil window; while Guaguaquí River-s1 samples exhibit
261 $\%20S$ and $\%\beta\beta$ values (Table 2) ranging from 0.52 to 0.55 and from 0.67 to 0.71, suggesting that
262 the respective equilibrium stages have been also reached, which would be indicative of a minimum
263 thermal maturity level equivalent to the peak oil generation (Peters et al., 2005). Several aromatic
264 hydrocarbon-based maturity parameters have been also calculated for the study samples (Table 2),
265 showing consistent behaviour among them. These compounds are present in all the samples except
266 those from the Minero River section. The main methylphenanthrene-based ratio (MPI-1; Radke and
267 Welte, 1983; Radke et al., 1986) shows very similar behaviour in most samples (see Table 2). The
268 values of such parameter denote that samples from Guaguaquí River-s3, west and east Lengupá

269 River sections have entered the condensate/wet gas window (see Table 2); while the remaining
270 samples, excluding those from Chitamena River ($MPI-1 \leq 0.91$), show $MPI-1$ values suggestive of
271 the peak to late oil window ($MPI-1 > 0.85$). In condensate window samples, the
272 dimethylphenanthrene (DMP) distribution has higher relative abundances of 2,3-DMP and 1-
273 ethylphenanthrene than that of the oil window samples (Fig. 3A). Also, the abundance of
274 trimethylphenanthrenes is extremely low in wet gas/condensate window samples compared with
275 those of the other samples except those from Minero River (Fig. 3A; Radke and Welte, 1983).

276

277 The MAI and MDI indices (Chen et al., 1996) have been calculated for numerous samples (Fig.
278 3B). The MAI index seems to overall increase with measured VR values (Table 2). Samples from
279 La Zambra Reserve, Hatalaguna River, Guaguaquí River-s2 and -s4 have values ranging from 0.48
280 to 0.65. Instead, Guaguaquí River-s3, west and east Lengupá River have values higher than 0.69
281 and up to 0.90. The behaviour of the MDI index is not distinct. Thus, samples with the highest MDI
282 values correspond to Guaguaquí River-s3, west and east Lengupá River averaging 0.46, 0.53, and
283 0.60, respectively; whilst samples from Hatalaguna River, Guaguaquí River-s2 and -s4, as well as
284 La Zambra Reserve average the respective values: 0.29, 0.30, 0.31, and 0.30. In comparison with
285 measured VR values, the MAI and MDI ratios increase up to a VR of c.a. 2% (Schultz et al., 2001).

286

287 **4.2. Organic matter source and depositional paleo-environments**

288 4.2.1. Carbon isotope, Rock-Eval, and V/Ni data

289 Even though the Rock-Eval hydrogen index (HI) is influenced by maturity (Espitalié et al., 1977)
290 and can sometimes vary given the same kerogen type (Cornford et al., 1998), this parameter allows
291 comparing the hydrocarbon potential of source rocks of similar maturity levels. In Chitamena River,
292 by considering two groups of samples per separate (the samples from the top of the section,
293 stratigraphic positions above 151 m, and those at levels below 90 m), samples from the upper part
294 of the section have higher HI values (313.68 mg HC/g TOC on average) than those from the lower

295 part (≤ 200 mg HC/g TOC). Present-day HI values in Guaguaquí River-s1 are in the 141.50-
296 181.31 mg HC/g TOC range (Table 1). When comparing the sections which are in the late oil
297 window among them (Table 1), Guaguaquí River-s4 has an average HI of 80.18 mg HC/g TOC,
298 which is slightly higher than that of Guaguaquí River-s2 (78.34 mg HC/g TOC). At the opposite
299 end, samples from Lower La Zambra Reserve and Hatalaguna River have HI values lower than 55
300 mg HC/g TOC. The Upper La Zambra Reserve sub-section exhibits, in part, HI values near or
301 above 100 mg HC/g TOC (levels below 29.2 m); whilst the top two samples have lower HI and S2
302 values (c.a. 25 mg HC/g TOC and ≤ 0.33 mg HC/g rock; Table 1). The wet gas window mature
303 samples from Guaguaquí River-s3, as well as west and east Lengupá River show average HI values
304 of 30.44, 23.48, and 10.07 mg HC/g TOC (Table 1). Lastly, even though Minero River section has
305 notable TOC values (> 1 wt.%), these samples depict no present-day oil hydrocarbon potential (S2
306 ≤ 0.07 mg HC/g rock and HI < 3.37 mg HC/g TOC).

307

308 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ kerogen data is shown in Table 2. Among the studied sections, carbon isotopic values ranging
309 from -28 to -25‰ were obtained in the samples from Guaguaquí River (except G5 and G6; OEA2
310 interval?), La Zambra Reserve, Hatalaguna River, and Chitamena River (excluding CH1 and
311 CH2). The west and east Lengupá River sections are isotopically heavier than the previous sections,
312 with $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values from -22.48 to -24.50‰; whilst Minero River section samples show the highest
313 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (around -21 ‰). V/Ni values (Table 3) have been also calculated to provide reliable
314 information in the metagenesis samples and others.

315

316 4.2.2. Molecular-based source-related proxies

317 As biomarkers (steranes and triterpanes), *n*-alkanes, and isoprenoids are only relatively intact, and
318 therefore reliable for source characterization in samples from the early to peak oil window (Peters et
319 al., 2005), the distribution of these compounds was investigated in Chitamena River and Guaguaquí
320 River-s1 sections, from the so-called proximal and distal regions, respectively. Several source-

321 related parameters were used to assess the type of precursor organic matter and depositional paleo-
322 environments (Table 3). Steranes and hopanes are intact in the Chitamena River, but these
323 biomarkers tend to be partially depleted in Guaguaquí River-s1, particularly in the slightly more
324 mature sediments towards the top of this sub-section (Figs. 4 and 5). Regarding the relative
325 abundances of C₂₇-C₂₈-C₂₉ regular steranes, all samples from Chitamena River and Guaguaquí
326 River-s1 are characterised by low C₂₈ abundances and, generally, slightly higher abundance of C₂₇
327 in comparison to their C₂₉ homologues (Fig. 4). Diahopane and oleanane were present in samples
328 from Chitamena River and pre-OEA2 Guaguaquí River-s1, but not notably high, while
329 bisnorhopane can be also identified as a ubiquitous compound in the Chitamena River samples (Fig.
330 5; peak identifications in the appendix). Regarding the distribution of the C₁₉ to C₂₁ cheilanthanes,
331 in Chitamena River two distinct trends are observed (Fig. 5): some samples from the lower part of
332 the section are characterised by a C₁₉>C₂₀>C₂₁ pattern, along with abundant C₂₄ tetracyclic
333 triterpene, while samples from the top of the column (interval “I” described in Table 1) follow the
334 C₁₉<C₂₀<C₂₁ pattern. In Guaguaquí River-s1, negligible differences can be observed in cheilanthane
335 distributions throughout the column, although only some samples clearly show the presence of
336 extended cheilanthanes up to C₃₅ (Fig. 5).

337

338 In Chitamena River, relatively higher contributions of long-chain *n*-alkanes were found towards the
339 bottom of the section (interval “III” described in Table 1), although in general, the *n*-alkane profile
340 exhibits maximum peaks from *n*-C₁₃ to *n*-C₁₆ (Fig. 6). In Guaguaquí River-s1, the *n*-alkane
341 distribution patterns are dominated by short-chain homologues (< *n*-C₁₉; Fig. 6). Chitamena River
342 and Guaguaquí River-s1 also show remarkably different pristane/phytane ratios: in the first section,
343 pristane/phytane ratios are between 1.91 and 3.02 (Table 3); instead, in the second section,
344 pristane/phytane ratios are between 0.94 and 1.09 (Table 3). In addition, only two Chitamena River
345 samples (CH7 and CH8) from the “II” interval show a prominent compound eluting between *n*-C₂₂
346 and *n*-C₂₃ in the *m/z* 57 mass chromatograms of the saturated fraction, which can be tentatively

347 identified as a C₂₇H₅₄ alkylated cyclohexane based on its mass spectra (molecular ion *m/z* 278; see
348 Fig. 6). Its significance in terms of source organic matter is not clear.

349

350 In all the studied sections, certain aromatic-based source-related proxies were also calculated.
351 Values for dibenzothiophene/phenanthrene (DBT/P) and three-fluorenes ratio or the quotient
352 between fluorene and the sum of three aromatic compounds (dibenzothiophene, dibenzofuran, and
353 fluorene) are shown in Table 3. Similarly, three diamondoid-based ratios were determined in the
354 rock extracts analyzed (Table 3): the ratio of dimethyladamantanes (DMA) to trimethyladamantanes
355 (TMA), ethyladamantane index (EAI), and dimethyldiamantane index-1 (DMDI-1).

356

357 **5. Discussion**

358 **5.1. Thermal maturity interpretation**

359 The combination of T_{max} data, VR measurements and molecular-based parameters offers a general
360 picture of the thermal maturity of the study sedimentary rocks, in which five distinct maturity
361 ranges are represented (Table 2). Chitamena River is the least mature section: most indicators
362 (except MPI-1 index) suggest a thermal maturity at the beginning of the peak oil window. In this
363 section, maturity levels show a slight increase towards the bottom, below 151 m. All the Chitamena
364 River samples show MPI-1 values > 0.55 (MPI-based VR values above 0.73%), but this parameter
365 has been described as not be accurate in predominantly marine organic matter at early maturation
366 stages (Cassani et al., 1988). Second, thermal maturity indicators also suggest that Guaguaquí
367 River-s1 samples are situated very close to the peak of oil generation. Third, Guaguaquí River-s2
368 and -s4 samples, together with those from La Zambra Reserve and Hatalaguna River sections have
369 similar thermal maturity levels at the late oil window. The measured VR data for Hatalaguna River
370 is lower (0.96% on average) than calculated values generally exceeding 1.10%, but as this section
371 has low TOC contents (Table 1), inaccurate measurements occur (Tyson, 1984). It is also noted the
372 fact that methylphenanthrene-based parameters cannot be applied to numerous samples from La

373 Zambera Reserve and Hatalaguna River (Table 2) since these latter samples exhibited depleted
374 aromatic profiles due to water washing under weathering conditions (Charrié-Duhaut et al., 2000).
375 Several Guaguaquí River-s3, west and east Lengupá River samples are characterised by yielding
376 very little bitumen, even though TOC contents are high in these rocks. All information indicates the
377 maturity levels of these latter samples in the condensate/wet gas window.

378

379 In the Guaguaquí River section, the notion that younger sediments are more mature than other older
380 ones can tentatively suggest that a second maturity event is linked to tectonic efforts or
381 hydrothermal fluids (Mahoney, 2018). Lastly, the Minero River samples contain very low amounts
382 of bitumen, even though their TOC values exceed 1 wt. %, suggesting maturity levels at the dry gas
383 window (Miles, 1989). In the case of the Minero River section, molecular parameters (including
384 diamondoid ratios) did not add reliable maturity information, but TAI values slightly higher than
385 3.5 corroborated that both representative samples reached the metagenesis stage (Staplin, 1977).

386

387 **5.2. Organic matter sources and depositional redox conditions**

388 **5.2.1 Precursor organic material and depositional settings**

389 Most Chitamena River samples have HI values from around 200 to 500 mg HC/g TOC (Table 1)
390 and S2/S3 ratios in the range of 5-10, suggesting type II/III source rocks with only a fair potential
391 for oil generation (Peters, 1986). By contrast, samples CH1 and CH2 have HI values clearly inferior
392 to 200 mg HC/g TOC (Table 2) and S2/S3 ratios ranging from 3 to 5, thus indicating predominantly
393 gas-prone kerogen (Baskin, 1997). Noteworthy is that lower HI data suggests higher terrestrial
394 contents (Langford and Blanc-Valleron, 1990), though HI also decreases with increasing maturity
395 levels (Killops et al., 1998). Based on TOC and HI values, kerogen type II and good potential for oil
396 generation could be inferred in Guaguaquí River-s1. Similarly, late oil window Guaguaquí River-s2
397 and -s4 sediments could be notably oil-prone based on HI values (Table 1); however, very low HI
398 values from some highly mature samples from the La Zambera Reserve and Hatalaguna River

399 sections can be observed. In this case, it remains unclear what effect the water-washing process has
400 on kerogens: S2 yields might be lowered because of this alteration process (Copard et al., 2002).

401

402 Biomarker and *n*-alkane distribution patterns for Chitamena River and Guaguaquí River-s1 rock
403 extracts showed a series of common characteristics. The *n*-alkane profiles with maximum peaks
404 between *n*-C₁₃ and *n*-C₁₈ (see Fig. 6) are typical of predominantly marine source rocks (Tissot and
405 Welte, 1984). Also, C₂₆/C₂₅ cheilanthane ratios around 1 (Table 3) indicate marine to transitional
406 sources rather than lacustrine or hypersaline conditions, which is confirmed by a lack of β-carotane
407 squalane, and gammacerane (Grice et al., 1998; Sinninghe Damsté et al., 1995), as well as by
408 C₃₁R/C₃₀ hopane ratios above 0.24 (Peters et al., 2005). The predominance of C₂₇ regular steranes
409 over their C₂₉ homologues together with tentative presence of C₃₀ regular steranes supports a
410 notable bacterial/planktonic contribution typical marine source rocks (Fig. 4; Grantham and
411 Wakefield, 1988). In more detail, some samples from the bottom of the Chitamena River section
412 exhibited the highest C₂₉ relative abundances, suggesting a greater terrigenous input (Moldowan et
413 al., 1985); while others from the upper part (post-OAE2) of the Guaguaquí River-s1 section showed
414 abundant extended cheilanthanes, which can be explained by the least terrestrial contribution (De
415 Grande et al., 1993) and increasing thermal maturity (Peters et al., 1990). Nevertheless, the presence
416 of oleanane, a biomarker of angiosperms (Moldowan et al., 1994), in most Chitamena River and
417 Guaguaquí River-s1 extracts, along with significant amounts of the C₁₉ and C₂₀ cheilanthanes
418 relative to their C₂₃ homologue (Fig. 5), would suggest an appreciable terrestrial contribution (Reed,
419 1977). This apparent contradiction denotes that Chitamena River and Guaguaquí River-s1 samples
420 appear to be sourced by a mixed assemblage of both marine plankton and land plant-derived
421 organic matter. Proximal and even distal paleo-environments might result in some land-plant
422 material preserved in marine settings.

423

424 The combination of one of the dimethyldiamantane-based parameters (DMDI-1) and the index with
425 ethyladamantane isomers (EAI) was also used as source markers to differentiate type II and type III
426 kerogens: DMD-1 and EAI are said to increase in terrestrially derived organic matter (Schulz et al.,
427 2001). According to Wingert (1992), both indices have a strong maturity influence (a decrease in
428 their values) and are only usefully applied to oil window samples ($VR < 1.35\%$). In our study case,
429 Chitamena River and Hatalaguna River samples show values of DMD-1 and EAI ranging from 69%
430 to 77% and from 75% to 82% (Table 3), respectively, suggesting a mixture of terrestrial and
431 marine sources (type II/III kerogen). By contrast, La Zambra Reserve and most Guaguaquí River
432 samples exhibit DMD-1 and EAI values in the 62-67% and 68-73% ranges, respectively, which
433 may reflect a predominantly marine precursor organic matter (type II kerogen). Thus, the results of
434 these two indices in the oil window samples would be in line with that of Schulz et al. (2001). The
435 relative abundances of dimethyladamantanes and trimethyladamantanes have been studied in all the
436 samples, as the predominance of DMA over TMA hydrocarbons has been reported in marine rather
437 than terrestrial organic matter (Gordadze 2008). As shown in Table 3, west/east Lengupá River,
438 Chitamena River/Hatalaguna River, and the rest exhibited low (<0.70), intermediate ($0.73-0.85$),
439 and high (> 0.98) DMA/TMA values, which would corroborate terrestrial, mixed marine/terrestrial,
440 and marine sources, respectively. As for the behaviour of this latter parameter with thermal
441 maturation, we do see differences between marine and terrestrial organic material at similar oil-
442 window and wet gas/condensate levels of maturity. The three-fluorenes ratio can be also useful to
443 infer characteristics of the palaeo-environment or source of the organic matter (Li et al., 2015). As
444 introduced, abundant dibenzothiophene is typical of marine depositional environments (Lin and
445 Wang, 1991). Instead, dibenzofuran has been proposed to be a marker for lichens (Radke et al.,
446 2000), while high relative abundances of fluorene suggest terrestrial and transitional settings (Li et
447 al., 2013). Though in Li et al. (2015) it is stated that this proxy, in principle, only works up to the
448 end of the oil window: dibenzofuran is found to be less maturity stable and decreases clearly from
449 VR values around 1.35%; in this dataset, the application range seems to be extended up to the

450 condensate window and even the beginning of the metagenesis stage. As shown in Table 3, the
451 samples from the Guaguaquí River, La Zambra Reserve and Minero River sections are defined by
452 having three-fluorenes ratios not exceeding 0.24, as it would correspond to marine shaly sediments.
453 Instead, in samples from the west and east Lengupá River, fluorene is the most abundant (values >
454 0.6), supporting fluvial/deltaic environments and high contribution from terrestrial sources; while
455 the ratios for the rest (0.28-0.43) denoted intermediate contributions.

456

457 Molecular-based parameters and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (-28 to -25‰) for Guaguaquí River and La Zambra
458 Reserve correspond to Cretaceous marine organic material (Dean et al., 1986); while the
459 isotopically heaviest and most mature organic matter in Minero River does not apparently
460 correspond to marine sources. In this regard, thermal maturity and other processes can affect the
461 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values, producing isotopic fractionation (e.g., Galimov, 2006). Among the sections in the
462 eastern foothills, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values for the west and east Lengupá River, but not those all for the
463 transitional Chitamena River and Hatalaguna River, are consistent with data from Dean et al. (1986)
464 for terrestrially dominated Cretaceous organic matter. Two samples from the bottom of the
465 Chitamena River section (CH1 and CH2) showed $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values superior to -25‰, which might reflect
466 lower sea levels and/or more influence of runoff (Sarmiento, 2001).

467

468 5.2.2 Paleo-redox conditions and source lithology

469 Biomarker work in Guaguaquí River-s1 and Chitamena River has also provided information on
470 rock lithologies and redox conditions. As shown in Table 3 and Figure 5, $\text{C}_{22}/\text{C}_{21}$ cheilanthane
471 ratios below 0.3, non-high 30-norhopane/hopane ratios (0.54-0.66), relatively high diasterane ratios
472 (0.29-0.41), $\text{C}_{24}/\text{C}_{23}$ cheilanthane ratios near or above 0.7, presence of diahopane, and
473 predominance of C_{34} extended hopane over its C_{35} counterpart are confirmatory of siliciclastic
474 sediments deposited under oxygen-depleted to dysoxic conditions (Mello et al., 1988; Moldowan et
475 al., 1991; Peters and Moldowan, 1991; Van Kaam-Peters et al., 1998; Peters et al., 2005). However,

476 Guaguaquí River-s1 and Chitamena River extracts showed marked geochemical differences. Thus,
477 pristane/phytane (Pr/Ph) ratios about 1 (Table 3) for Guaguaquí River-s1 extracts indicate that they
478 were derived from sources deposited in a paleo-environment under oxygen-depleted conditions;
479 while higher Pr/Ph values (2-3) for Chitamena River samples would indicate dysoxic conditions
480 (Volkman and Maxwell, 1986). In Guaguaquí River-s1, the Pr/Ph ratio may be expected to have
481 been modified by processes such as thermal maturation (Brooks et al., 1969; Dzou et al., 1995), but
482 despite this, these values are low and can be used here to indicate the depositional conditions.

483 As shown in Figure 7, Chitamena River and Guaguaquí River-t1 extracts could be grouped in the
484 zones that correspond to oxidising and reducing depositional settings, respectively. Another of the
485 distinctive features of Chitamena River samples was that 28,30-bisnorhopane was only present in
486 them (Fig. 5), which might denote in this case laminated shaly sedimentary rocks rather than anoxic
487 carbonate sources (Brincat and Abbot, 2001), particularly towards the top of the section with
488 decreasing maturity (Moldowan et al., 1984). A previous study of pyrite morphologies and iron
489 speciation (Mahoney, 2018) discarded anoxic conditions in the Chitamena River section.

490

491 Both dibenzothiophene-to-phenanthrene and pristane-to-phytane ratios, as well as the total sulfur
492 content (St), can be used for investigating redox conditions or lithology of source rocks (Skrȩt and
493 Fabiańska, 2009). When combining dibenzothiophene/phenanthrene ratios and sulfur contents being
494 low (<0.5 and <0.4%; see Table 3) for the study sediments, all of them were found to correspond to
495 marine siliciclastic environments, as was to be expected. It was not observed a clear trend of the
496 DBT/P ratio with thermal maturation (Table 3), thereby suggesting that this indicator can be used
497 for redox conditions regardless of maturity levels. In the least mature Guaguaquí River-s1 and
498 Chitamena River columns, low DBT/P values and Pr/Ph ranging from 1 to 3 are related to marine
499 shales and oxygen-depleted to dysoxic conditions, where sulfide availability is absent or low
500 (Hughes et al., 1995).

501

502 Low sulfur contents ($< 0.4\%$) and V/Ni ratios above 0.11 for all the samples excepting those from
503 the east Lengupá River section (Table 3) suggest that the majority of sections have sedimentary
504 rocks which were deposited in marine-terrestrial settings under low-oxygen (V/Ni about 2) to
505 dysoxic conditions (Lewan, 1984; Galarraga et al., 2008); while the east Lengupá River samples
506 could be related to oxygenated bottom waters ($V/Ni \leq 0.11$). When carbonate facies are deposited
507 under reducing conditions, bacterial sulfide is not completely sequestered by iron ions and nickel
508 ions precipitate in metal sulfides rather than form metal-organic compounds, contrarily to stable
509 vanadyl ions, leading to high V/Ni ratios (>3). However, during deposition of shaly facies under
510 oxidant conditions, iron ions react with sulfide ions, thus forming pyrite, whereas nickel ions form
511 metal-organic compounds, leading to low V/Ni ratios (Lewan, 1984). Even though Ni and V
512 contents can be affected by processes such as weathering and thermal maturation, V/Ni remains
513 constant due to the similar structures and high thermal stabilities of metal-organic compounds that
514 contain both metals (Lewan and Maynard, 1982). Despite the little bitumen yields (Table 2), V/Ni
515 was determined in Marine River extracts assuming that they are mostly composed of porphyrin-rich
516 polar constituents at overmature stages (Mackenzie, 1984), along with the notion that porphyrinic
517 components account for a notable portion of both metals in the rock extracts (Escobar et al., 2012).

518

519 Finally, based on $\delta^{13}C$ values, in the middle part of Guaguaquí River-s1, samples G5 and G6
520 (depths from 144 to 151 m) are identified to depict isotopically higher values than the rest of the
521 sub-section, representing a shift of $\sim 3.5\%$ towards more positive values (-23.49% on average;
522 Table 2). This carbon isotopic excursion (CIE), rather than a change in source type input (similar
523 biomarker signatures throughout the column; Table 3), might be tentatively taken as an evidence of
524 the latest Cenomanian OAE2 positive carbon isotopic excursion (CIE) in the geological record
525 (Schlanger et al., 1987). An OAE seems to be also coherent with higher TOC contents and lower
526 Pr/Ph in this part of the column (Ghassal et al., 2016). It is noted that whilst some redox indicators
527 have their highest values associated to such CIE (e.g. sulfur content, see Table 3), redox conditions

528 did not changed enormously after the OAE on the basis of such and other redox indicators (DBT/P
529 and Pr/Ph) so that oxygen-deprived conditions prevailed also after the event.

530

531 **5.3. Integrating information in the basinal context**

532 5.3.1. Source successions in the study areas

533 After syn-rift deposition of Macanal and Cumbre units at Valanginian times in the study sub-region,
534 the Hauterivian, thermal subsidence occurred coinciding with the beginning of a regional
535 transgression that was interrupted by local regression episodes. This is represented by Las Juntas
536 Formation and clastic beds in Rosablanca sequence in the foothills of the East-Andean Cordillera
537 (Horton et al., 2010). Following the thermal post-rift subsidence stage, the transgression was
538 intensified and these clastics were overlayed by the Barremian-Aptian Paja and Fomeque
539 formations (Villamil, 1998), in the so-called proximal and distal areas from this study
540 (corresponding to the eastern and western foothills of the Eastern Cordillera). These units are
541 represented in Minero River, west and east Lengupá River. Most results suggest outstanding initial
542 oil potential (type II kerogen) in the Paja Formation deposited in oxygen-depleted settings, which
543 agrees with previous data addressing the potential of this unit in the Eastern Cordillera (Gaona-
544 Narváez et al., 2013). Nonetheless, the Minero River section has unusually high $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (Fig.
545 8), which do not agree with previously described Cretaceous marine isotopic signatures (Dean et al.,
546 1986). As for the Fomeque Formation, a higher terrestrial input (kerogen type III) and oxic
547 depositional conditions are found in the upper part of the unit corresponding to the east Lengupá
548 River section, while the bottom (west Lengupá River) shows less negative $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ data and overall
549 reflects a slightly lower predominance of terrestrial contribution (kerogen type II/III-III). During
550 middle to late Cretaceous times, the study sub-region consisted of a marine margin with the main
551 terrestrial input coming from the Guyana Shield (Macellari and De Vries, 1987), which is reflected
552 in lower terrestrial contributions in the distal area.

553

554 Organic matter deposition at the Cenomanian is represented by the Une and Guaguaquí units in
555 proximal and distal areas, respectively. Very good oil generative potentials (kerogen type II) were
556 obtained for Guaguaquí samples, while the less oil prone shaly sedimentary rocks of Une Formation
557 were deposited in a more oxygen-enriched and transitional paleo-environment (kerogen type II/III-
558 III), on the basis of Rock-Eval data (TOC, HI and S2/S3 of 1 wt%, 220 mg HC/g TOC and ~5) as
559 well as other geochemical results (Table 3) prior to this work (Cuñado, 2012). Within Guaguaquí
560 River-s1, the OAE2 event can be proposed based on a positive CIE (Fig. 8) and enhanced TOC
561 contents. This is consistent with the transgressive episode which prevailed for Cenomanian-
562 Turonian times, leading to anoxic conditions in most of the Eastern Cordillera (Spickert, 2014). It
563 seems that whilst globally, the sea-level fell during the Turonian (Schlanger et al., 1987), the
564 regional configuration of the study sub-region still favoured high sea levels (Villamil, 1998).

565

566 Chitamena River/Hatalaguna River sections in the proximal area and Guaguaquí River-s4/Lower La
567 Zambara Reserve sections in the distal area cover, respectively, the age-equivalent late Turonian-
568 early Santonian Chipaque Formation and Lower Olini Group. Predictably, whereas organic
569 matter of marine origin is clearly dominant (kerogen type II) in the Lidita Inferior Member (Olini
570 Group); for Hatalaguna River and, to a lesser extent, Chitamena River, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (Fig. 7) and
571 other results suggest a transitional depositional environment with a notable input of marine organic
572 material (kerogen type II/III). Lastly, during the Campanian, the configuration in this sub-region
573 coincided with the beginning of a regional sea-level fall due to the incipient uplift of the Eastern
574 Cordillera, nonetheless subsidence continued with the deposition of the Guadalupe and Córdoba
575 formations in the proximal and distal areas, respectively (Sarmiento, 2001). Whilst TOC, HI and
576 S2/S3 values (2.2 wt%, 120 mg HC/g TOC and 3) along with other previous geochemical evidences
577 (Table 3; Cuñado, 2012) suggest that the shaly Guadalupe Formation is characterized by terrigenous
578 (kerogen type III) sediments deposited under oxidizing conditions, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of the Córdoba unit

579 (Fig. 8) indicate that this unit is marine-dominated (kerogen type II) and can be related to low-
580 oxygen bottom waters.

581

582 5.3.2. Linking thermal maturity to stratigraphy

583 It should be noted that there seems to be a direct link between stratigraphic position and maturity
584 level in the eastern foothills: pre-Barremian strata, Barremian-Aptian Fomeque source rocks, lower
585 intervals (Turonian-Coniacian) of the Chipaque unit, and upper segments (Coniacian-Santonian) of
586 this latter reached the metagenesis stage, wet gas/condensate window, late oil window, and early oil
587 window, respectively; while the Albian-Cenomanian Une and Campanian Guadalupe formations
588 have maturity levels equivalent to the peak and early oil generation (see Table 2; Cuñado, 2012). In
589 regards to the western foothills, Barremian-Aptian Paja and older sediments also reached the
590 metagenesis stage; however, contrary to expectations, the Campanian Córdoba unit and Coniacian-
591 Santonian Lower Olini sediments are more mature (late oil window) than the upper part
592 (Cenomanian-Turonian) of the Guaguaquí Group (peak oil generation). Noteworthy is that the
593 earliest Cretaceous strata reached the metagenesis stage regardless of the study area; whereas higher
594 variability of thermal maturity in the uppermost Cretaceous sediments is observed: most of the less
595 mature sediments are of Coniacian to Santonian age and younger in the eastern foothills. By
596 contrast, in the western foothills, results show that older strata are not necessarily more mature
597 during the Late Cretaceous, it seems that maturity is at least partly linked to deformation processes
598 and/or associated volcanism in this part of the Boyacá Department (Palmer and Russell, 1988).

599

600 **6. Conclusions**

601 Characterization of thermal maturity of the shaly rocks in the foothills of Eastern Cordillera
602 (Boyacá province) corroborates the assumption of most of them having high maturity levels. Source
603 rocks in the western foothills covers a different range of maturity levels, from peak oil window to

604 metagenesis stage, compared with those in the eastern foothills varying early oil window to wet
605 gas/condensate window.

606

607 Most of the study Barremian to Campanian shaly rocks are marine-dominated (predominantly type
608 II organic matter) in the western foothills, of which Guaguaquí shales and one interval of Cordoba
609 sediments seem to have had considerable oil potential. A CIE is interpreted to tentatively reflect the
610 Cenomanian-Turonian OAE2 in the Guaguaquí Group and such oxygen-deprived conditions would
611 have prevailed after the anoxic event. Among the proximal studied shales, type II/III and III
612 kerogens are represented, and the upper part of the Fomeque Formation (type III kerogen), though
613 in the wet gas/condensate window, might be identified to have had a considerable gas potential.
614 Bisnorhopane appears to be a ubiquitous component in the Chipaque unit from the studied
615 Chitamena River section, which overall shows Type II-III kerogen of only fair hydrocarbon
616 potential. Finally, two source proxies (three-fluorene ratio and the quotient of dimethyladamantanes
617 to trimethyladamantanes) proved to be useful here to discriminate more terrestrial versus marine-
618 dominated organic matter in the study sediments up to the initial metagenesis stage (VR~2%).

619

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622

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939 Figure 1: Map showing the location of Boyacá sub-region in the Eastern Cordillera of Colombia, including
940 the two study areas, sampling sites and the Cónдор-1 borehole (4.727° N, 73.135° W). Sampling points
941 coordinates: Minero River (5.657° N, 74.094° W); Guaguaquí River (5.829° N, 74.321° W); Hatalaguna River
942 (5.591° N, 72.915° W); La Zambra Reserve (5.810° N, 74.239° W); Chitamena River (4.962° N, 72.911°
943 W); East Lengupá River (4.869° N, 73.181 °W); and West Lengupá River (4.841° N, 73.201° W).

944

945 Figure 2: Cretaceous stratigraphic records and sampling intervals at the western and eastern foothills. Notes:
946 CH: Chitamena River, H: Hatalaguna River, EL: East Lengupá River, WL: West Lengupá River, Upper Z:
947 La Zambra River upper, Lower Z: La Zambra River Lower, G s4: Guaguaquí River-s4, G s1: Guaguaquí
948 River-s1 (Guaguaquí River-s2 and -s3 (without clear age control) are between s1 and s4). M: Minero River.

949 Figure 3: A and B, respectively, combined m/z 178+192+206+220 ion chromatograms for the aromatic
950 fraction as well as m/z 135 and 187 ion chromatograms for the saturate fraction of representative samples at
951 increasing thermal maturity. The x-axis and y-axis represent retention time (min) and abundance
952 (counts).Notes: 1=phenanthrene; 2=3-methylphenanthrene (MP); 3=2-MP; 4=9-MP; 5=1-MP; 6=1-
953 ethylphenanthrene; 7=2,6+2,7+3,5-dimethylphenanthrene (DMP); 8=1,3+2,10+3,9+3,10-DMP;
954 9=1,6+2,5+2,9-DMP; 10=1,7-DMP; 11=2,3-DMP; 12=1,9+9,4+4,10-DMP; 13=1,8-DMP; 14=1,2-DMP;
955 1'=1-methyladamantane (MA); 2'=2-MA; 3'=1-ethyladamantane (EA); 4'=2-EA; 5'=4-methyldiamantane
956 (MD); 6'=1-MD; and 7'=3-MD.

957 Figure 4: Representative m/z 217 mass chromatograms from the saturated fractions of selected samples from
958 Chitamena River and Guaguaquí River-s1. The x-axis and y-axis represent retention time (min) and
959 abundance (counts).

960 Figure 5: Representative m/z 191 mass chromatograms from the saturated fractions of selected samples from
961 Chitamena River and Guaguaquí River-s1. The x-axis and y-axis represent retention time (min) and
962 abundance (counts).

963 Figure 6: Representative mass chromatograms m/z 57 of the saturated fractions of selected samples from
964 Chitamena River and Guaguaquí River-s1; as well as peak 'a' mass spectrum. The x-axis and y-axis
965 represent retention time (min) and abundance (counts).

966 Figure 7: Plot of Pr/n-C₁₇ versus Ph/n-C₁₈ for Chitamena River and Guaguaquí River-s1 to assess redox
967 conditions and type of precursor organic material (Shanmugam, 1985).

968 Figure 8: Box plots of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰) values of kerogens over time in the source rocks of the sampled
969 sections or sub-sections in the study distal and proximal areas.

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Organic geochemical investigation of Cretaceous source rocks with varying thermal maturity levels in the East Andes (Boyacá, Colombia)

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Abstract: This study encompasses a geochemical investigation of Cretaceous source rocks from the Eastern Cordillera (Colombia). This basin represents an interesting area for geochemical studies due to its abundance of organic matter-rich levels, some of which exhibit mild to extremely high thermal maturities, enabling discussion on long-term carbon sinks. This research work focuses on the study of organic-rich shaly sediments of Berremian to Campanian age from seven (7) outcrop locations in two areas of the Boyacá Department. A set of seventy (70) rock samples have been analysed using several organic geochemical techniques and have shown to cover thermal maturity ranges from the early oil window to the metagenesis stage (measured reflectance values from 0.6% to 2.1%). The OAE2 event was identified based on a 2.5‰ to 3‰ carbon isotopic excursion in the distal Guaguaquí Group from the section along the Guaguaquí River. Maturity was not found to correlate with depositional burial depths in the so-called distal study area, suggesting that other tectonic events may have played an important role in the genetic history of hydrocarbons particularly in this part of the Boyacá Department. During the mid-to late Cretaceous times, the two study areas consisted of a marine margin with a terrestrial input from the east, which is reflected in a higher terrestrial character of sediments in the eastern foothills (V/Ni < 0.7) compared to the others. Finally, fluorene- and diamondoid-based components were used for enhancing the characterization of the mid-to late Cretaceous organic matter in terms of source in the study sub-region (three-fluorenes and dimethyl-/trimethyl-adamantanes ratios above or below 0.25 and 0.85).

Keywords: Cretaceous source rocks, Eastern Cordillera, thermal maturity, precursor organic matter, diamondoids

1. Introduction

The Eastern Cordillera, of ca. 60.000 km², has constituted one of the most prolific petroleum producing regions of Colombia and northern South America along with the Llanos and Middle and Upper Magdalena Basins (e.g., Sánchez et al., 2015). Commercial oil exploration in the area started in the mid-1920s, motivated by the abundant number of oil seeps found in the basin (Ramón et al., 2001; Aguilera et al., 2010). Within the region, multiple source rock levels are identified, of pre-Cretaceous to Tertiary age, which are mainly located in the Magdalena and Eastern Cordillera (e.g. Palmer and Russell, 1988). Among these, it is remarkable the number of lower to upper Cretaceous organic-rich levels exhibiting fair to excellent generation potential.

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35 During the Cretaceous period, organic-rich layers were deposited across the territory now
36 recognized as Colombia, forming a foreland basin in the latest Cretaceous (Cooper et al., 1995;
37 Villamil, 1998). The regional configuration resulted in a wide variety of paleo-depositional
38 environments, leading to lateral and vertical changes in organic source and richness (Blanco-
39 Velandia, 2012). Subsequently, extensive sediment thicknesses and volcanism associated with
40 compressional tectonics led to high thermal maturities of the organic-rich sediments (Mora et al.,
41 2010). Based on these assessments, the Colombian East Andes cover an interesting region for
42 petroleum geochemical studies, allowing for the evaluation of organic geochemistry in shaly facies
43 representing different levels of thermal maturity and types of organic matter.

44 In the Boyacá sub-region (Fig. 1), gas- and oil-prone Cretaceous shale-rich intervals have been
45 identified as probable source rocks of fair to excellent generative potential in the eastern and
46 western foothills of the East-Andean Cordillera, respectively: the Fomeque (TOC > 1%) and Paja
47 (TOC below 3% on average) formations in the late Barremian and Aptian times (Gaona-Narváz et
48 al., 2013), the Une (TOC in the 2-8% range) and Guaguaquí (TOC > 2%) facies deposited in the
49 Albian-Cenomanian period (Zavala et al., 2009); Turonian-Santonian source rocks (TOC > 4%) of
50 the Chipaque Formation and Olini Group (Blanco-Velandia, 2012), and infrequent organic-rich
51 strata of the Campanian Guadalupe and Cordoba formations (Palmer and Russell, 1988; Moretti et
52 al., 2009). Among the Barremian to Campanian stratigraphic units under study, the Chipaque
53 formation and Guaguaquí group have been reported to contain locally good source potential in the
54 Eastern Cordillera (Ramón et al., 2001). They both were deposited during periods of sea level
55 highstand, partly coinciding with the latest Cenomanian-early Turonian oceanic anoxic event
56 (OEA2); therefore, some of the highest organic carbon contents in these facies are associated with
57 OAE2 (Villamil, 1998).

58

59 Newly sampled lower to upper Cretaceous organic-rich rocks collected from the western and
60 eastern foothills of the Eastern Cordillera (here referred as distal and proximal areas corresponding

61 to different paleo-depositional environments as stated by Guerrero and Sarmiento in 1996) are the
62 target study. Until now no studies have been conducted on Cretaceous shales of different maturity
63 levels and proximal to distal palaeo-settings in Boyacá province for recognizing reliable parameters
64 based on aromatic biomarkers and diamondoid-related ratios for source characterization in highly
65 mature sediments. In this regard, the present research work is of interest to investigate
66 lateral/vertical variations in the paleo-depositional conditions of Cretaceous organic-rich strata
67 within the study area in the Colombian Eastern Andes and, simultaneously, to assess molecular
68 geochemical parameters at varying (particularly high) thermal maturation levels after comparing
69 samples from two areas associated with distal and proximal settings at similar levels of maturity.

70

71 This work focuses on the organic geochemical study of Cretaceous sediments from the foothills of
72 the East-Andean Cordillera. The two studied areas are located in the Boyacá Department
73 (Colombia), roughly 85 km north and 55 km northeast of Bogotá city, respectively (Fig. 1). The
74 aims of the present study are: (i) enhancing the characterization of thermal maturities, sources, and
75 depositional settings of the Cretaceous sediments in the Boyacá sub-region; (ii) comparing the
76 characteristics of different age-equivalent rock intervals between Barremian and Campanian times
77 corresponding to the two areas under study in the Boyacá Department; and (iii) integrating the
78 source and paleo-environment information obtained into its geological/stratigraphic context. All this
79 information will be useful to improve the models of the paleo-deposition of the study Cretaceous
80 organic-rich sediments in the study sub-region and their petroleum generation history.

81

82 **2. Geological background**

83 The Eastern Cordillera constitutes the eastern mountain range of the Colombian Andes (Fig. 1). Its
84 structure consists of a double-verging fold-and-thrust belt ranging NE-SW of mostly Mesozoic
85 marine sediments placed over a Precambrian-Paleozoic polydeformed basement. The boundaries of
86 the Eastern Cordillera are defined by igneous/metamorphic rocks from the Santander Massif in the

87 north, the Algeciras-Garzón fault system in the south, and the Middle/Upper Magdalena and the
88 Llanos foreland basins in the west and east, respectively (e.g., Cooper et al., 1995, Restrepo-Pace et
89 al., 2004).

90

91 The genesis of the Colombian Andes has its initiation in the subduction of the Caribbean and Nazca
92 oceanic plates beneath the South America continental lithospheric plate (Taboada et al., 2000). The
93 geological history of the Eastern Cordillera (from the Late Jurassic to today) comprises four stages
94 (Cooper et al., 1995; Moreno-López and Escalona, 2015): (i) during Early Cretaceous times (up to
95 Hauterivian), the terminal rifting phase, rift basins progressively developed inland due to the
96 separation of the North and South America plates (NW-SE stress) and progressive opening of the
97 Caribbean Sea; (ii) a period of thermal post-rift subsidence and incipient transgression occurred
98 from Hauterivian to early Albian in a back-arc setting, where normal faults still controlled the
99 turbiditic-dominated deposition during this stage; (iii) the intensification of the transgressive
100 episode, coinciding with an Albian-late Coniacian period of low tectonic activity, which resulted in
101 the development of a vast regional retro-arc basin in which the deposition of the main Cretaceous
102 source rocks took place; (iv) a regional sea-level fall occurred, coinciding with the uplift of the
103 ancestral Central Cordillera (Santonian-Maastrichtian), which led to the beginning of a regressive
104 sequence; and (v) lastly, as convergence rates increased, compressional tectonics led progressively
105 to the inversion of Mesozoic faults, uplift of the Eastern Cordillera and partitioning of the regional
106 foreland depression into the Magdalena and Llanos foreland basins.

107

108 Throughout almost the entire Cretaceous period, the Eastern Cordillera consisted of a sedimentary
109 basin whose configuration and sediment-type accumulation evolved roughly from being terrigenous
110 synrift-dominated (Berriasian-Valanginian) to regionally spread marine-dominated (late Aptian-
111 Maastrichtian; Villamil, 1998). Maximum palaeo-water depths in the Boyaca sub-region were
112 reached around the Cenomanian-Turonian boundary, when the main Cretaceous source rocks were

113 deposited in a marine margin which extended from Peru to Venezuela (Villamil, 1998). The main
114 continental supply came from the Guyana Shield (i.e. from the east; that is why our eastern study
115 area is called proximal) and greater accommodation space was created towards the west and north.

116

117 In the so-called distal area or western foothills (Fig. 1), the Cretaceous covers ages from Late
118 Valanginian to Campanian-Maastrichtian (Fig. 2) and tends to be folded in wide structures and
119 faulted (inverse SW-NE faults dipping SE; Rangel et al., 1996). The Paja Formation consists of
120 mostly black calcareous and highly micaceous shales (Gaona-Narváez et al., 2013), and it is
121 traditionally correlated with the Fomeque Formation from the eastern flank of the Eastern
122 Cordillera (Moretti et al., 2009). The Puerto Romero Formation comprises dark grey limestones
123 alternating with black claystones (Rodríguez and Ulloa, 1994). The locally named Guaguaquí
124 Group represents the sedimentation of black micaceous shales with limestones, siltstones, and
125 cherts (Mahoney, 2018). The Olini Group is characterized as a two-package succession of
126 calcareous siltstones with alternating siliceous siltstones and cherts known as Lidita Superior and
127 Lidita Inferior), which are intercalated with a package of grey mudstones. Finally, the Cordoba
128 Formation consists mostly of dark grey calcareous siltstones (Rodríguez and Ulloa, 1994). In the
129 proximal area or eastern foothills, the Cretaceous is almost fully represented (Berriasian to
130 Maastrichtian; Fig. 2), with the youngest sediments outcropping towards the northwest. Within this
131 area, in the southern part the Cretaceous tends to be folded in symmetric and wide structures, whilst
132 towards the north, the tectonic complexity increases, and the structures are narrower. The Macanal
133 Formation mostly consists of calcareous shales with intercalated sandstone levels and depicts
134 thermal maturity in the metagenesis stage (Mahoney, 2018). The Las Juntas Formation is defined by
135 two sequences of quartz sandstones with interbedded black shales intercalated by a package of
136 black shales (Rodríguez and Ulloa, 1994). The Fomeque unit consists of grey to black shales
137 alternating with limestone, sandstone, and cherts (Moretti et al., 2009). The Une Formation
138 comprises quartz arenites interbedded with thin layers of mudstones, siltstones, and marly shales

139 (Zavala et al., 2009). The Chipaque unit is described as an intercalation of black shales and
140 siltstones with siliceous sands and scarce limestones (García et al., 2025). The overlying Guadalupe
141 Formation consists of quartz arenites and greywackes alternating with scarce levels of coaly shales
142 and cherts (Sarmiento, 2001). Lastly, the Guaduas unit comprises mainly shales with sandstone and
143 coal beds (Valenzuela, 2002).

144

145 **3. Samples and methods**

146 3.1. Samples pre-selected

147 A set of seventy (70) pre-selected rock samples were collected from seven outcrop locations (Fig.
148 1), which cover most of the Cretaceous in the foothills of the East-Andean Cordillera of Colombia.
149 These are distributed as follows: in the proximal area (eastern foothills), 13, 12, 5 and 5
150 representative samples were collected from the sections near the Chitamena River (PE), between the
151 Hatalaguna River and the village of Llano de Alarcón (H), along the west (WL) and east (EL) sides
152 of the Lengupá River; in the distal area (western foothills), 2, 23, and 10 samples were also
153 collected from the sections near the Minero River and San Pablo de Borbur village (M), between
154 the Guaguaquí River and Puerto Romero city (G), and close to the La Zambra Reserve (Z). This
155 latter section and the previous one are subdivided in lower/upper parts and in four segments named
156 s1, s2, s3, and s4, respectively. The sampling interval of each section or sub-section under study in
157 the respective stratigraphic record is shown in Figure 2. The lithological descriptions of samples are
158 compiled in the Table 1. For comparison purposes, data on two cores, one of them from the
159 Guadalupe unit (3360-3364 m depth) and the other from the Une Formation (4188-4190 m depth),
160 of the El Cóndor-1 borehole (see Fig. 1; Cuñado, 2012), located in the eastern foothills, have been
161 also considered. Experimental work was performed in the facilities of the Geological Research
162 Center of Guayaquil, except isotopic analyses at the Andalusian Earth Sciences Institute (Granada).

163

164 3.2. Analytical methods

165 3.2.1. Screening analyses

166 First, aliquots of samples (approximately 5 g each) were dried at 40 °C for 24 hours, pulverized in
167 an agate mortar and treated with a 1 M HCl solution to remove the carbonates and sulfates (Verardo
168 et al., 1990). Later, 60 mg aliquots of each powdered rock were run in a LECO CS-300 instrument
169 for TOC contents. Vitrinite reflectance (VR) analyses were performed on some aliquots of ca. 5 g of
170 dried rock sample (40°C for 48 hours). Rock-Eval pyrolysis of samples was done using a Delsi II
171 Rock Eval equipment. These latter measurements were performed using 60 mg aliquots of the
172 carbonate-free powdered rock, and the basic methodology was used (Espitalié et al., 1977). About
173 120 g of selected rock samples were pulverized after being rinsed with petroleum ether, and then
174 extraction of the bitumen was performed on a Soxhlet apparatus (93:7 v/v of dichloromethane and
175 methanol) for 48 h. About 1.5 g of activated copper was added to the mixture of solvents to capture
176 tiny residues of elemental sulphur during the extraction of the rock. Bitumen was concentrated
177 using a rotavapor instrument to 10 ml (temperature <20 °C) and a small homogenized aliquot
178 (0.6 ml) was taken for extractable organic matter (EOM) measurements. Lastly, for determining
179 maturity levels of the Minero River samples, TAI (thermal alteration index; Staplin, 1977) was also
180 determined in amorphous organic matter (Peters et al., 1977).

181

182 3.2.2. Bitumen analyses

183 Previous separation of asphaltenes by using *n*-heptane in a 1:40 v/v ratio, saturated and aromatic
184 hydrocarbons were then fractionated by liquid chromatography (De la Cruz et al., 1997). The
185 aliphatic hydrocarbons were eluted with *n*-hexane, the aromatics with toluene, and the resins with
186 toluene/methanol (70:30 v/v) using a column filled with silica-alumina. Both fractions were
187 analysed by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), in full scan and selected ion
188 monitoring (SIM) modes. Before performing GC-MS analyses of lower diamondoids on samples,
189 saturate fractions of representative rock extracts were treated with ZSM-5 zeolite to remove *n*-
190 alkanes (He et al., 2012). An Agilent 7890A gas chromatogram with a HP-5 fused silica capillary

191 column (30 m length; 0.25 mm ID, 0.25 μm film thickness), coupled to a 5975C mass spectrometer
192 was used. Samples (1 μl) were auto injected with splitless injection. Helium was used as a carrier
193 gas, operated at a constant flow of 1 ml/min. The oven was programmed from an initial temperature
194 of 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (3 min initial hold time), to a final temperature of 310 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, at a constant rate of 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$
195 (20 min final hold time). The mass spectrometer was operated in electron ionization mode (EI) at
196 70 eV. Data processing was done with Chemstation software. On an aliquot of each bitumen
197 extract, sulfur content and V/Ni ratio were determined using an energy dispersive X-ray Panalytical
198 Axios spectrometer and a Perkin Elmer Optima 3000 DV inductively coupled plasma optical
199 emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) system, respectively.

200

201 3.2.2. Isotopic analysis

202 After kerogen isolation of ca. 3g of pulverized rock samples following the procedure designed by
203 Durand and Nicaise (1980), kerogen concentrates were placed in precombusted tin cups and
204 oxidized (combustion furnace held at 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) in a Thermo Finnigan 1112 Elemental Analyzer
205 interfaced to a Finnigan MAT Delta V Mass Spectrometer for determination of C isotopic data.
206 Some of the samples were run in duplicates and standard deviations were below 0.12. The $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$
207 data is reported as $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values, relative to the Vienna Peedee Belemnite (VPDB). Standards used
208 were IA-001 (wheat flour), IA-R005 (beet sugar), and IA-R006 (cane sugar), which were evenly
209 intercalated between the samples.

210

211 4. Results

212 4.1. Thermal maturity characterization

213 4.1.1. Measured vitrinite reflectance and bitumen yield.

214 A wide range of T_{max} values is represented in the samples analyzed, from 427 to 603 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Table 2).
215 Among the stratigraphic columns, Chitamena River section averages the lowest T_{max} value (434 $^{\circ}\text{C}$),
216 followed by Guaguaquí River-s1 (454 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), and other five (Guaguaquí River-s2 and -s4, Hatalaguna

217 River, as well as Upper and Lower La Zambra Reserve) average T_{max} in the range 460-470 °C.
218 Further, Guaguaquí River-s3, as well as west and east Lengupá River samples have T_{max} values
219 around or exceeding 500°C. Lastly, Minero River samples correspond to residual S2 yields below
220 0.1 mg HC/g rock which are interpreted as leading to an inaccurate T_{max} of 493°C (Peters, 1986).
221
222 Measured vitrinite reflectance (VR) values also vary among a subset of the studied samples from
223 0.57% to 2.07% (Table 2). Chitamena River section (Chipaque unit) shows the lowest average
224 (0.59%); followed by Hatalaguna River (0.96%), Guaguaquí River-s1 (0.93%), Lower and Upper
225 La Zambra Reserve (1.05 and 1.07%, respectively), Guaguaquí River-s4 (1.27%) and -s2 (1.33%);
226 Guaguaquí River-s3 has an average VR value of 1.69%, while west and east Lengupá River
227 sections (Fomeque Formation), respectively, average 1.74% and 1.88%. Samples from the Minero
228 River section (Paja Formation) have an average measured VR value of 2.03%.
229
230 Significant amounts of EOM (averaging values > 4 mg HC/g rock) are obtained in Upper La
231 Zambra Reserve section (Córdoba Formation), Guaguaquí River-s1 and -s2 (Guaguaquí unit), as
232 well as -s4 (Lower Olini Group) and some of the Hatalaguna River samples (Table 2). The
233 Chitamena River samples have EOM values averaging 3.43 mg HC/g rock. The samples from
234 Lower La Zambra Reserve (Lower Olini Group), west Lengupá River, Guaguaquí River-s3
235 (Guaguaquí unit), and some of the Hatalaguna River section (Chipaque unit) exhibit lower EOM
236 abundances compared to the latter ones (Table 2). The amount of EOM is expected to increase in
237 early to peak oil source rocks and to decrease after the late oil window (Miles, 1989). Lastly,
238 several samples yielded very little EOM or bitumen below the detection limit of the scale and are
239 indicated in Table 2 as <0.15 mg HC/g rock. These correspond to all the analysed east Lengupá
240 River and Minero River samples, as well as some from west Lengupá River. In these three sections,
241 TOC contents are not negligible (Table 1). Thus, the low bitumen amounts are here interpreted as a
242 sign of thermal over-maturation rather than poor organic matter contents.

243

244 4.1.2. Molecular maturity parameters

245 Molecular maturity indicators (Table 3), including biomarkers, diamondoid-based, and aromatic
246 parameters, have been investigated in the study sediments to obtain additional maturity assessment.
247 Note that some of these parameters could not be calculated in some samples (e.g. Minero River
248 section), as these components were absent or not well-resolved in the saturated or aromatic
249 fractions. Also, even though in some other cases saturated, aromatic, and diamondoid compounds
250 could be resolved, certain parameters were not suitable for assessing thermal maturation because
251 their levels of thermal maturity do not correspond to their application range (e.g. some aromatic
252 hydrocarbons in Chitamena River or diamondoids in Minero River, west and east Lengupá River
253 sections).

254

255 Excluding a few marginally mature samples from the top of the Chitamena River section, with
256 values of 22S% < 57% (see Table 2), all the samples exhibit homohopane isomerization values
257 (%22S) in the 0.57-0.62 range, indicating that the corresponding equilibrium stage has been reached
258 (Peters et al., 2005), and these rocks have entered the oil window. In Chitamena River, sterane
259 isomerization ratios (%20S and %ββ) averaging 40% and 32%, respectively, would indicate
260 maturity levels at the beginning of the oil window; while Guaguaquí River-s1 samples exhibit
261 %20S and %ββ values (Table 2) ranging from 0.52 to 0.55 and from 0.67 to 0.71, suggesting that
262 the respective equilibrium stages have been also reached, which would be indicative of a minimum
263 thermal maturity level equivalent to the peak oil generation (Peters et al., 2005). Several aromatic
264 hydrocarbon-based maturity parameters have been also calculated for the study samples (Table 2),
265 showing consistent behaviour among them. These compounds are present in all the samples except
266 those from the Minero River section. The main methylphenanthrene-based ratio (MPI-1; Radke and
267 Welte, 1983; Radke et al., 1986) shows very similar behaviour in most samples (see Table 2). The
268 values of such parameter denote that samples from Guaguaquí River-s3, west and east Lengupá

269 River sections have entered the condensate/wet gas window (see Table 2); while the remaining
270 samples, excluding those from Chitamena River ($MPI-1 \leq 0.91$), show MPI-1 values suggestive of
271 the peak to late oil window ($MPI-1 > 0.85$). In condensate window samples, the
272 dimethylphenanthrene (DMP) distribution has higher relative abundances of 2,3-DMP and 1-
273 ethylphenanthrene than that of the oil window samples (Fig. 3A). Also, the abundance of
274 trimethylphenanthrenes is extremely low in wet gas/condensate window samples compared with
275 those of the other samples except those from Minero River (Fig. 3A; Radke and Welte, 1983).

276

277 The MAI and MDI indices (Chen et al., 1996) have been calculated for numerous samples (Fig.
278 3B). The MAI index seems to overall increase with measured VR values (Table 2). Samples from
279 La Zambra Reserve, Hatalaguna River, Guaguaquí River-s2 and -s4 have values ranging from 0.48
280 to 0.65. Instead, Guaguaquí River-s3, west and east Lengupá River have values higher than 0.69
281 and up to 0.90. The behaviour of the MDI index is not distinct. Thus, samples with the highest MDI
282 values correspond to Guaguaquí River-s3, west and east Lengupá River averaging 0.46, 0.53, and
283 0.60, respectively; whilst samples from Hatalaguna River, Guaguaquí River-s2 and -s4, as well as
284 La Zambra Reserve average the respective values: 0.29, 0.30, 0.31, and 0.30. In comparison with
285 measured VR values, the MAI and MDI ratios increase up to a VR of c.a. 2% (Schultz et al., 2001).

286

287 **4.2. Organic matter source and depositional paleo-environments**

288 4.2.1. Carbon isotope, Rock-Eval, and V/Ni data

289 Even though the Rock-Eval hydrogen index (HI) is influenced by maturity (Espitalié et al., 1977)
290 and can sometimes vary given the same kerogen type (Cornford et al., 1998), this parameter allows
291 comparing the hydrocarbon potential of source rocks of similar maturity levels. In Chitamena River,
292 by considering two groups of samples per separate (the samples from the top of the section,
293 stratigraphic positions above 151 m, and those at levels below 90 m), samples from the upper part
294 of the section have higher HI values (313.68 mg HC/g TOC on average) than those from the lower

295 part (≤ 200 mg HC/g TOC). Present-day HI values in Guaguaquí River-s1 are in the 141.50-
296 181.31 mg HC/g TOC range (Table 1). When comparing the sections which are in the late oil
297 window among them (Table 1), Guaguaquí River-s4 has an average HI of 80.18 mg HC/g TOC,
298 which is slightly higher than that of Guaguaquí River-s2 (78.34 mg HC/g TOC). At the opposite
299 end, samples from Lower La Zambra Reserve and Hatalaguna River have HI values lower than 55
300 mg HC/g TOC. The Upper La Zambra Reserve sub-section exhibits, in part, HI values near or
301 above 100 mg HC/g TOC (levels below 29.2 m); whilst the top two samples have lower HI and S2
302 values (c.a. 25 mg HC/g TOC and ≤ 0.33 mg HC/g rock; Table 1). The wet gas window mature
303 samples from Guaguaquí River-s3, as well as west and east Lengupá River show average HI values
304 of 30.44, 23.48, and 10.07 mg HC/g TOC (Table 1). Lastly, even though Minero River section has
305 notable TOC values (> 1 wt.%), these samples depict no present-day oil hydrocarbon potential (S2
306 ≤ 0.07 mg HC/g rock and HI < 3.37 mg HC/g TOC).

307

308 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ kerogen data is shown in Table 2. Among the studied sections, carbon isotopic values ranging
309 from -28 to -25‰ were obtained in the samples from Guaguaquí River (except G5 and G6; OEA2
310 interval?), La Zambra Reserve, Hatalaguna River, and Chitamena River (excluding CH1 and
311 CH2). The west and east Lengupá River sections are isotopically heavier than the previous sections,
312 with $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values from -22.48 to -24.50‰; whilst Minero River section samples show the highest
313 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (around -21 ‰). V/Ni values (Table 3) have been also calculated to provide reliable
314 information in the metagenesis samples and others.

315

316 4.2.2. Molecular-based source-related proxies

317 As biomarkers (steranes and triterpanes), *n*-alkanes, and isoprenoids are only relatively intact, and
318 therefore reliable for source characterization in samples from the early to peak oil window (Peters et
319 al., 2005), the distribution of these compounds was investigated in Chitamena River and Guaguaquí
320 River-s1 sections, from the so-called proximal and distal regions, respectively. Several source-

321 related parameters were used to assess the type of precursor organic matter and depositional paleo-
322 environments (Table 3). Steranes and hopanes are intact in the Chitamena River, but these
323 biomarkers tend to be partially depleted in Guaguaquí River-s1, particularly in the slightly more
324 mature sediments towards the top of this sub-section (Figs. 4 and 5). Regarding the relative
325 abundances of C₂₇-C₂₈-C₂₉ regular steranes, all samples from Chitamena River and Guaguaquí
326 River-s1 are characterised by low C₂₈ abundances and, generally, slightly higher abundance of C₂₇
327 in comparison to their C₂₉ homologues (Fig. 4). Diahopane and oleanane were present in samples
328 from Chitamena River and pre-OEA2 Guaguaquí River-s1, but not notably high, while
329 bisnorhopane can be also identified as a ubiquitous compound in the Chitamena River samples (Fig.
330 5; peak identifications in the appendix). Regarding the distribution of the C₁₉ to C₂₁ cheilanthanes,
331 in Chitamena River two distinct trends are observed (Fig. 5): some samples from the lower part of
332 the section are characterised by a C₁₉>C₂₀>C₂₁ pattern, along with abundant C₂₄ tetracyclic
333 triterpene, while samples from the top of the column (interval “I” described in Table 1) follow the
334 C₁₉<C₂₀<C₂₁ pattern. In Guaguaquí River-s1, negligible differences can be observed in cheilanthane
335 distributions throughout the column, although only some samples clearly show the presence of
336 extended cheilanthanes up to C₃₅ (Fig. 5).

337

338 In Chitamena River, relatively higher contributions of long-chain *n*-alkanes were found towards the
339 bottom of the section (interval “III” described in Table 1), although in general, the *n*-alkane profile
340 exhibits maximum peaks from *n*-C₁₃ to *n*-C₁₆ (Fig. 6). In Guaguaquí River-s1, the *n*-alkane
341 distribution patterns are dominated by short-chain homologues (< *n*-C₁₉; Fig. 6). Chitamena River
342 and Guaguaquí River-s1 also show remarkably different pristane/phytane ratios: in the first section,
343 pristane/phytane ratios are between 1.91 and 3.02 (Table 3); instead, in the second section,
344 pristane/phytane ratios are between 0.94 and 1.09 (Table 3). In addition, only two Chitamena River
345 samples (CH7 and CH8) from the “II” interval show a prominent compound eluting between *n*-C₂₂
346 and *n*-C₂₃ in the *m/z* 57 mass chromatograms of the saturated fraction, which can be tentatively

347 identified as a C₂₇H₅₄ alkylated cyclohexane based on its mass spectra (molecular ion *m/z* 278; see
348 Fig. 6). Its significance in terms of source organic matter is not clear.

349

350 In all the studied sections, certain aromatic-based source-related proxies were also calculated.
351 Values for dibenzothiophene/phenanthrene (DBT/P) and three-fluorenes ratio or the quotient
352 between fluorene and the sum of three aromatic compounds (dibenzothiophene, dibenzofuran, and
353 fluorene) are shown in Table 3. Similarly, three diamondoid-based ratios were determined in the
354 rock extracts analyzed (Table 3): the ratio of dimethyladamantanes (DMA) to trimethyladamantanes
355 (TMA), ethyladamantane index (EAI), and dimethyldiamantane index-1 (DMDI-1).

356

357 **5. Discussion**

358 **5.1. Thermal maturity interpretation**

359 The combination of T_{max} data, VR measurements and molecular-based parameters offers a general
360 picture of the thermal maturity of the study sedimentary rocks, in which five distinct maturity
361 ranges are represented (Table 2). Chitamena River is the least mature section: most indicators
362 (except MPI-1 index) suggest a thermal maturity at the beginning of the peak oil window. In this
363 section, maturity levels show a slight increase towards the bottom, below 151 m. All the Chitamena
364 River samples show MPI-1 values > 0.55 (MPI-based VR values above 0.73%), but this parameter
365 has been described as not be accurate in predominantly marine organic matter at early maturation
366 stages (Cassani et al., 1988). Second, thermal maturity indicators also suggest that Guaguaquí
367 River-s1 samples are situated very close to the peak of oil generation. Third, Guaguaquí River-s2
368 and -s4 samples, together with those from La Zambra Reserve and Hatalaguna River sections have
369 similar thermal maturity levels at the late oil window. The measured VR data for Hatalaguna River
370 is lower (0.96% on average) than calculated values generally exceeding 1.10%, but as this section
371 has low TOC contents (Table 1), inaccurate measurements occur (Tyson, 1984). It is also noted the
372 fact that methylphenanthrene-based parameters cannot be applied to numerous samples from La

373 Zambera Reserve and Hatalaguna River (Table 2) since these latter samples exhibited depleted
374 aromatic profiles due to water washing under weathering conditions (Charrié-Duhaut et al., 2000).
375 Several Guaguaquí River-s3, west and east Lengupá River samples are characterised by yielding
376 very little bitumen, even though TOC contents are high in these rocks. All information indicates the
377 maturity levels of these latter samples in the condensate/wet gas window.

378

379 In the Guaguaquí River section, the notion that younger sediments are more mature than other older
380 ones can tentatively suggest that a second maturity event is linked to tectonic efforts or
381 hydrothermal fluids (Mahoney, 2018). Lastly, the Minero River samples contain very low amounts
382 of bitumen, even though their TOC values exceed 1 wt. %, suggesting maturity levels at the dry gas
383 window (Miles, 1989). In the case of the Minero River section, molecular parameters (including
384 diamondoid ratios) did not add reliable maturity information, but TAI values slightly higher than
385 3.5 corroborated that both representative samples reached the metagenesis stage (Staplin, 1977).

386

387 **5.2. Organic matter sources and depositional redox conditions**

388 **5.2.1 Precursor organic material and depositional settings**

389 Most Chitamena River samples have HI values from around 200 to 500 mg HC/g TOC (Table 1)
390 and S2/S3 ratios in the range of 5-10, suggesting type II/III source rocks with only a fair potential
391 for oil generation (Peters, 1986). By contrast, samples CH1 and CH2 have HI values clearly inferior
392 to 200 mg HC/g TOC (Table 2) and S2/S3 ratios ranging from 3 to 5, thus indicating predominantly
393 gas-prone kerogen (Baskin, 1997). Noteworthy is that lower HI data suggests higher terrestrial
394 contents (Langford and Blanc-Valleron, 1990), though HI also decreases with increasing maturity
395 levels (Killops et al., 1998). Based on TOC and HI values, kerogen type II and good potential for oil
396 generation could be inferred in Guaguaquí River-s1. Similarly, late oil window Guaguaquí River-s2
397 and -s4 sediments could be notably oil-prone based on HI values (Table 1); however, very low HI
398 values from some highly mature samples from the La Zambera Reserve and Hatalaguna River

399 sections can be observed. In this case, it remains unclear what effect the water-washing process has
400 on kerogens: S2 yields might be lowered because of this alteration process (Copard et al., 2002).

401

402 Biomarker and *n*-alkane distribution patterns for Chitamena River and Guaguaquí River-s1 rock
403 extracts showed a series of common characteristics. The *n*-alkane profiles with maximum peaks
404 between *n*-C₁₃ and *n*-C₁₈ (see Fig. 6) are typical of predominantly marine source rocks (Tissot and
405 Welte, 1984). Also, C₂₆/C₂₅ cheilanthane ratios around 1 (Table 3) indicate marine to transitional
406 sources rather than lacustrine or hypersaline conditions, which is confirmed by a lack of β-carotane
407 squalane, and gammacerane (Grice et al., 1998; Sinninghe Damsté et al., 1995), as well as by
408 C₃₁R/C₃₀ hopane ratios above 0.24 (Peters et al., 2005). The predominance of C₂₇ regular steranes
409 over their C₂₉ homologues together with tentative presence of C₃₀ regular steranes supports a
410 notable bacterial/planktonic contribution typical marine source rocks (Fig. 4; Grantham and
411 Wakefield, 1988). In more detail, some samples from the bottom of the Chitamena River section
412 exhibited the highest C₂₉ relative abundances, suggesting a greater terrigenous input (Moldowan et
413 al., 1985); while others from the upper part (post-OAE2) of the Guaguaquí River-s1 section showed
414 abundant extended cheilanthanes, which can be explained by the least terrestrial contribution (De
415 Grande et al., 1993) and increasing thermal maturity (Peters et al., 1990). Nevertheless, the presence
416 of oleanane, a biomarker of angiosperms (Moldowan et al., 1994), in most Chitamena River and
417 Guaguaquí River-s1 extracts, along with significant amounts of the C₁₉ and C₂₀ cheilanthanes
418 relative to their C₂₃ homologue (Fig. 5), would suggest an appreciable terrestrial contribution (Reed,
419 1977). This apparent contradiction denotes that Chitamena River and Guaguaquí River-s1 samples
420 appear to be sourced by a mixed assemblage of both marine plankton and land plant-derived
421 organic matter. Proximal and even distal paleo-environments might result in some land-plant
422 material preserved in marine settings.

423

424 The combination of one of the dimethyldiamantane-based parameters (DMDI-1) and the index with
425 ethyladamantane isomers (EAI) was also used as source markers to differentiate type II and type III
426 kerogens: DMD-1 and EAI are said to increase in terrestrially derived organic matter (Schulz et al.,
427 2001). According to Wingert (1992), both indices have a strong maturity influence (a decrease in
428 their values) and are only usefully applied to oil window samples ($VR < 1.35\%$). In our study case,
429 Chitamena River and Hatalaguna River samples show values of DMD-1 and EAI ranging from 69%
430 to 77% and from 75% to 82% (Table 3), respectively, suggesting a mixture of terrestrial and
431 marine sources (type II/III kerogen). By contrast, La Zambra Reserve and most Guaguaquí River
432 samples exhibit DMD-1 and EAI values in the 62-67% and 68-73% ranges, respectively, which
433 may reflect a predominantly marine precursor organic matter (type II kerogen). Thus, the results of
434 these two indices in the oil window samples would be in line with that of Schulz et al. (2001). The
435 relative abundances of dimethyladamantanes and trimethyladamantanes have been studied in all the
436 samples, as the predominance of DMA over TMA hydrocarbons has been reported in marine rather
437 than terrestrial organic matter (Gordadze 2008). As shown in Table 3, west/east Lengupá River,
438 Chitamena River/Hatalaguna River, and the rest exhibited low (<0.70), intermediate ($0.73-0.85$),
439 and high (> 0.98) DMA/TMA values, which would corroborate terrestrial, mixed marine/terrestrial,
440 and marine sources, respectively. As for the behaviour of this latter parameter with thermal
441 maturation, we do see differences between marine and terrestrial organic material at similar oil-
442 window and wet gas/condensate levels of maturity. The three-fluorenes ratio can be also useful to
443 infer characteristics of the palaeo-environment or source of the organic matter (Li et al., 2015). As
444 introduced, abundant dibenzothiophene is typical of marine depositional environments (Lin and
445 Wang, 1991). Instead, dibenzofuran has been proposed to be a marker for lichens (Radke et al.,
446 2000), while high relative abundances of fluorene suggest terrestrial and transitional settings (Li et
447 al., 2013). Though in Li et al. (2015) it is stated that this proxy, in principle, only works up to the
448 end of the oil window: dibenzofuran is found to be less maturity stable and decreases clearly from
449 VR values around 1.35%; in this dataset, the application range seems to be extended up to the

450 condensate window and even the beginning of the metagenesis stage. As shown in Table 3, the
451 samples from the Guaguaquí River, La Zambra Reserve and Minero River sections are defined by
452 having three-fluorenes ratios not exceeding 0.24, as it would correspond to marine shaly sediments.
453 Instead, in samples from the west and east Lengupá River, fluorene is the most abundant (values >
454 0.6), supporting fluvial/deltaic environments and high contribution from terrestrial sources; while
455 the ratios for the rest (0.28-0.43) denoted intermediate contributions.

456

457 Molecular-based parameters and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (-28 to -25‰) for Guaguaquí River and La Zambra
458 Reserve correspond to Cretaceous marine organic material (Dean et al., 1986); while the
459 isotopically heaviest and most mature organic matter in Minero River does not apparently
460 correspond to marine sources. In this regard, thermal maturity and other processes can affect the
461 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values, producing isotopic fractionation (e.g., Galimov, 2006). Among the sections in the
462 eastern foothills, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values for the west and east Lengupá River, but not those all for the
463 transitional Chitamena River and Hatalaguna River, are consistent with data from Dean et al. (1986)
464 for terrestrially dominated Cretaceous organic matter. Two samples from the bottom of the
465 Chitamena River section (CH1 and CH2) showed $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values superior to -25‰, which might reflect
466 lower sea levels and/or more influence of runoff (Sarmiento, 2001).

467

468 5.2.2 Paleo-redox conditions and source lithology

469 Biomarker work in Guaguaquí River-s1 and Chitamena River has also provided information on
470 rock lithologies and redox conditions. As shown in Table 3 and Figure 5, $\text{C}_{22}/\text{C}_{21}$ cheilanthane
471 ratios below 0.3, non-high 30-norhopane/hopane ratios (0.54-0.66), relatively high diasterane ratios
472 (0.29-0.41), $\text{C}_{24}/\text{C}_{23}$ cheilanthane ratios near or above 0.7, presence of diahopane, and
473 predominance of C_{34} extended hopane over its C_{35} counterpart are confirmatory of siliciclastic
474 sediments deposited under oxygen-depleted to dysoxic conditions (Mello et al., 1988; Moldowan et
475 al., 1991; Peters and Moldowan, 1991; Van Kaam-Peters et al., 1998; Peters et al., 2005). However,

476 Guaguaquí River-s1 and Chitamena River extracts showed marked geochemical differences. Thus,
477 pristane/phytane (Pr/Ph) ratios about 1 (Table 3) for Guaguaquí River-s1 extracts indicate that they
478 were derived from sources deposited in a paleo-environment under oxygen-depleted conditions;
479 while higher Pr/Ph values (2-3) for Chitamena River samples would indicate dysoxic conditions
480 (Volkman and Maxwell, 1986). In Guaguaquí River-s1, the Pr/Ph ratio may be expected to have
481 been modified by processes such as thermal maturation (Brooks et al., 1969; Dzou et al., 1995), but
482 despite this, these values are low and can be used here to indicate the depositional conditions.

483 As shown in Figure 7, Chitamena River and Guaguaquí River-t1 extracts could be grouped in the
484 zones that correspond to oxidising and reducing depositional settings, respectively. Another of the
485 distinctive features of Chitamena River samples was that 28,30-bisnorhopane was only present in
486 them (Fig. 5), which might denote in this case laminated shaly sedimentary rocks rather than anoxic
487 carbonate sources (Brincat and Abbot, 2001), particularly towards the top of the section with
488 decreasing maturity (Moldowan et al., 1984). A previous study of pyrite morphologies and iron
489 speciation (Mahoney, 2018) discarded anoxic conditions in the Chitamena River section.

490

491 Both dibenzothiophene-to-phenanthrene and pristane-to-phytane ratios, as well as the total sulfur
492 content (St), can be used for investigating redox conditions or lithology of source rocks (Skrȩt and
493 Fabiańska, 2009). When combining dibenzothiophene/phenanthrene ratios and sulfur contents being
494 low (<0.5 and <0.4%; see Table 3) for the study sediments, all of them were found to correspond to
495 marine siliciclastic environments, as was to be expected. It was not observed a clear trend of the
496 DBT/P ratio with thermal maturation (Table 3), thereby suggesting that this indicator can be used
497 for redox conditions regardless of maturity levels. In the least mature Guaguaquí River-s1 and
498 Chitamena River columns, low DBT/P values and Pr/Ph ranging from 1 to 3 are related to marine
499 shales and oxygen-depleted to dysoxic conditions, where sulfide availability is absent or low
500 (Hughes et al., 1995).

501

502 Low sulfur contents ($< 0.4\%$) and V/Ni ratios above 0.11 for all the samples excepting those from
503 the east Lengupá River section (Table 3) suggest that the majority of sections have sedimentary
504 rocks which were deposited in marine-terrestrial settings under low-oxygen (V/Ni about 2) to
505 dysoxic conditions (Lewan, 1984; Galarraga et al., 2008); while the east Lengupá River samples
506 could be related to oxygenated bottom waters ($V/Ni \leq 0.11$). When carbonate facies are deposited
507 under reducing conditions, bacterial sulfide is not completely sequestered by iron ions and nickel
508 ions precipitate in metal sulfides rather than form metal-organic compounds, contrarily to stable
509 vanadyl ions, leading to high V/Ni ratios (>3). However, during deposition of shaly facies under
510 oxidant conditions, iron ions react with sulfide ions, thus forming pyrite, whereas nickel ions form
511 metal-organic compounds, leading to low V/Ni ratios (Lewan, 1984). Even though Ni and V
512 contents can be affected by processes such as weathering and thermal maturation, V/Ni remains
513 constant due to the similar structures and high thermal stabilities of metal-organic compounds that
514 contain both metals (Lewan and Maynard, 1982). Despite the little bitumen yields (Table 2), V/Ni
515 was determined in Marine River extracts assuming that they are mostly composed of porphyrin-rich
516 polar constituents at overmature stages (Mackenzie, 1984), along with the notion that porphyrinic
517 components account for a notable portion of both metals in the rock extracts (Escobar et al., 2012).

518

519 Finally, based on $\delta^{13}C$ values, in the middle part of Guaguaquí River-s1, samples G5 and G6
520 (depths from 144 to 151 m) are identified to depict isotopically higher values than the rest of the
521 sub-section, representing a shift of $\sim 3.5\%$ towards more positive values (-23.49% on average;
522 Table 2). This carbon isotopic excursion (CIE), rather than a change in source type input (similar
523 biomarker signatures throughout the column; Table 3), might be tentatively taken as an evidence of
524 the latest Cenomanian OAE2 positive carbon isotopic excursion (CIE) in the geological record
525 (Schlanger et al., 1987). An OAE seems to be also coherent with higher TOC contents and lower
526 Pr/Ph in this part of the column (Ghassal et al., 2016). It is noted that whilst some redox indicators
527 have their highest values associated to such CIE (e.g. sulfur content, see Table 3), redox conditions

528 did not changed enormously after the OAE on the basis of such and other redox indicators (DBT/P
529 and Pr/Ph) so that oxygen-deprived conditions prevailed also after the event.

530

531 **5.3. Integrating information in the basinal context**

532 5.3.1. Source successions in the study areas

533 After syn-rift deposition of Macanal and Cumbre units at Valanginian times in the study sub-region,
534 the Hauterivian, thermal subsidence occurred coinciding with the beginning of a regional
535 transgression that was interrupted by local regression episodes. This is represented by Las Juntas
536 Formation and clastic beds in Rosablanca sequence in the foothills of the East-Andean Cordillera
537 (Horton et al., 2010). Following the thermal post-rift subsidence stage, the transgression was
538 intensified and these clastics were overlayed by the Barremian-Aptian Paja and Fomeque
539 formations (Villamil, 1998), in the so-called proximal and distal areas from this study
540 (corresponding to the eastern and western foothills of the Eastern Cordillera). These units are
541 represented in Minero River, west and east Lengupá River. Most results suggest outstanding initial
542 oil potential (type II kerogen) in the Paja Formation deposited in oxygen-depleted settings, which
543 agrees with previous data addressing the potential of this unit in the Eastern Cordillera (Gaona-
544 Narváez et al., 2013). Nonetheless, the Minero River section has unusually high $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (Fig.
545 8), which do not agree with previously described Cretaceous marine isotopic signatures (Dean et al.,
546 1986). As for the Fomeque Formation, a higher terrestrial input (kerogen type III) and oxic
547 depositional conditions are found in the upper part of the unit corresponding to the east Lengupá
548 River section, while the bottom (west Lengupá River) shows less negative $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ data and overall
549 reflects a slightly lower predominance of terrestrial contribution (kerogen type II/III-III). During
550 middle to late Cretaceous times, the study sub-region consisted of a marine margin with the main
551 terrestrial input coming from the Guyana Shield (Macellari and De Vries, 1987), which is reflected
552 in lower terrestrial contributions in the distal area.

553

554 Organic matter deposition at the Cenomanian is represented by the Une and Guaguaquí units in
555 proximal and distal areas, respectively. Very good oil generative potentials (kerogen type II) were
556 obtained for Guaguaquí samples, while the less oil prone shaly sedimentary rocks of Une Formation
557 were deposited in a more oxygen-enriched and transitional paleo-environment (kerogen type II/III-
558 III), on the basis of Rock-Eval data (TOC, HI and S2/S3 of 1 wt%, 220 mg HC/g TOC and ~5) as
559 well as other geochemical results (Table 3) prior to this work (Cuñado, 2012). Within Guaguaquí
560 River-s1, the OAE2 event can be proposed based on a positive CIE (Fig. 8) and enhanced TOC
561 contents. This is consistent with the transgressive episode which prevailed for Cenomanian-
562 Turonian times, leading to anoxic conditions in most of the Eastern Cordillera (Spickert, 2014). It
563 seems that whilst globally, the sea-level fell during the Turonian (Schlanger et al., 1987), the
564 regional configuration of the study sub-region still favoured high sea levels (Villamil, 1998).

565

566 Chitamena River/Hatalaguna River sections in the proximal area and Guaguaquí River-s4/Lower La
567 Zambra Reserve sections in the distal area cover, respectively, the age-equivalent late Turonian-
568 early Santonian Chipaque Formation and Lower Olini Group. Predictably, whereas organic
569 matter of marine origin is clearly dominant (kerogen type II) in the Lidita Inferior Member (Olini
570 Group); for Hatalaguna River and, to a lesser extent, Chitamena River, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (Fig. 7) and
571 other results suggest a transitional depositional environment with a notable input of marine organic
572 material (kerogen type II/III). Lastly, during the Campanian, the configuration in this sub-region
573 coincided with the beginning of a regional sea-level fall due to the incipient uplift of the Eastern
574 Cordillera, nonetheless subsidence continued with the deposition of the Guadalupe and Córdoba
575 formations in the proximal and distal areas, respectively (Sarmiento, 2001). Whilst TOC, HI and
576 S2/S3 values (2.2 wt%, 120 mg HC/g TOC and 3) along with other previous geochemical evidences
577 (Table 3; Cuñado, 2012) suggest that the shaly Guadalupe Formation is characterized by terrigenous
578 (kerogen type III) sediments deposited under oxidizing conditions, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of the Córdoba unit

579 (Fig. 8) indicate that this unit is marine-dominated (kerogen type II) and can be related to low-
580 oxygen bottom waters.

581

582 5.3.2. Linking thermal maturity to stratigraphy

583 It should be noted that there seems to be a direct link between stratigraphic position and maturity
584 level in the eastern foothills: pre-Barremian strata, Barremian-Aptian Fomeque source rocks, lower
585 intervals (Turonian-Coniacian) of the Chipaque unit, and upper segments (Coniacian-Santonian) of
586 this latter reached the metagenesis stage, wet gas/condensate window, late oil window, and early oil
587 window, respectively; while the Albian-Cenomanian Une and Campanian Guadalupe formations
588 have maturity levels equivalent to the peak and early oil generation (see Table 2; Cuñado, 2012). In
589 regards to the western foothills, Barremian-Aptian Paja and older sediments also reached the
590 metagenesis stage; however, contrary to expectations, the Campanian Córdoba unit and Coniacian-
591 Santonian Lower Olini sediments are more mature (late oil window) than the upper part
592 (Cenomanian-Turonian) of the Guaguaquí Group (peak oil generation). Noteworthy is that the
593 earliest Cretaceous strata reached the metagenesis stage regardless of the study area; whereas higher
594 variability of thermal maturity in the uppermost Cretaceous sediments is observed: most of the less
595 mature sediments are of Coniacian to Santonian age and younger in the eastern foothills. By
596 contrast, in the western foothills, results show that older strata are not necessarily more mature
597 during the Late Cretaceous, it seems that maturity is at least partly linked to deformation processes
598 and/or associated volcanism in this part of the Boyacá Department (Palmer and Russell, 1988).

599

600 **6. Conclusions**

601 Characterization of thermal maturity of the shaly rocks in the foothills of Eastern Cordillera
602 (Boyacá province) corroborates the assumption of most of them having high maturity levels. Source
603 rocks in the western foothills covers a different range of maturity levels, from peak oil window to

604 metagenesis stage, compared with those in the eastern foothills varying early oil window to wet
605 gas/condensate window.

606

607 Most of the study Barremian to Campanian shaly rocks are marine-dominated (predominantly type
608 II organic matter) in the western foothills, of which Guaguaquí shales and one interval of Cordoba
609 sediments seem to have had considerable oil potential. A CIE is interpreted to tentatively reflect the
610 Cenomanian-Turonian OAE2 in the Guaguaquí Group and such oxygen-deprived conditions would
611 have prevailed after the anoxic event. Among the proximal studied shales, type II/III and III
612 kerogens are represented, and the upper part of the Fomeque Formation (type III kerogen), though
613 in the wet gas/condensate window, might be identified to have had a considerable gas potential.
614 Bisnorhopane appears to be a ubiquitous component in the Chipaque unit from the studied
615 Chitamena River section, which overall shows Type II-III kerogen of only fair hydrocarbon
616 potential. Finally, two source proxies (three-fluorene ratio and the quotient of dimethyladamantanes
617 to trimethyladamantanes) proved to be useful here to discriminate more terrestrial versus marine-
618 dominated organic matter in the study sediments up to the initial metagenesis stage (VR~2%).

619

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622

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937 Figure 1: Map showing the location of Boyacá sub-region in the Eastern Cordillera of Colombia, including the two
938 study areas, sampling sites and the Cónдор-1 borehole (4.727° N, 73.135° W). Sampling points coordinates: Minero
939 River (5.657° N, 74.094° W); Guaguaquí River (5.829° N, 74.321° W); Hatalaguna River (5.591° N, 72.915° W); La
940 Zambara Reserve (5.810° N, 74.239° W); Chitamena River (4.962° N, 72.911° W); East Lengupá River (4.869° N,
941 73.181° W); and West Lengupá River (4.841° N, 73.201° W).
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943 Figure 2: Cretaceous stratigraphic records and sampling intervals at the western and eastern foothills. Notes: CH:
944 Chitamena River, H: Hatalaguna River, EL: East Lengupá River, WL: West Lengupá River, Upper Z: La Zambara
945 River upper, Lower Z: La Zambara River Lower, G s4: Guaguaquí River-s4, G s1: Guaguaquí River-s1 (Guaguaquí
946 River-s2 and -s3 (without clear age control) are between s1 and s4). M: Minero River.

947 Figure 3: A and B, respectively, combined m/z 178+192+206+220 ion chromatograms for the aromatic fraction as well
948 as m/z 135 and 187 ion chromatograms for the saturate fraction of representative samples at increasing thermal
949 maturity. The x-axis and y-axis represent retention time (min) and abundance (counts).Notes: 1=phenanthrene; 2=3-
950 methylphenanthrene (MP); 3=2-MP; 4=9-MP; 5=1-MP; 6=1-ethylphenanthrene; 7=2,6+2,7+3,5-dimethylphenanthrene
951 (DMP); 8=1,3+2,10+3,9+3,10-DMP; 9=1,6+2,5+2,9-DMP; 10=1,7-DMP; 11=2,3-DMP; 12=1,9+9,4+4,10-DMP;
952 13=1,8-DMP; 14=1,2-DMP; 1'=1-methyladamantane (MA); 2'=2-MA; 3'=1-ethyladamantane (EA); 4'=2-EA; 5'=4-
953 methyladamantane (MD); 6'=1-MD; and 7'=3-MD.

954 Figure 4: Representative m/z 217 mass chromatograms from the saturated fractions of selected samples from
955 Chitamena River and Guaguaquí River-s1. The x-axis and y-axis represent retention time (min) and abundance
956 (counts).

957 Figure 5: Representative m/z 191 mass chromatograms from the saturated fractions of selected samples from Chitamena
958 River and Guaguaquí River-s1. The x-axis and y-axis represent retention time (min) and abundance (counts).

959 Figure 6: Representative mass chromatograms m/z 57 of the saturated fractions of selected samples from Chitamena
960 River and Guaguaquí River-s1; as well as peak 'a' mass spectrum. The x-axis and y-axis represent retention time (min)
961 and abundance (counts).

962 Figure 7: Plot of $Pr/n-C_{17}$ versus $Ph/n-C_{18}$ for Chitamena River and Guaguaquí River-s1 to assess redox conditions and
963 type of precursor organic material (Shanmugam, 1985).

964 Figure 8: Box plots of the $\delta^{13}C$ (‰) values of kerogens over time in the source rocks of the sampled sections or sub-
965 sections in the study distal and proximal areas.

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Figure 8

Appendix: Main triterpanes identified in the extracts.

1	C ₁₉ -Cheilanthane
2	C ₂₀ -Cheilanthane
3	C ₂₁ -Cheilanthane
4	C ₂₂ -Cheilanthane
5	C ₂₃ -Cheilanthane
6	C ₂₄ -Cheilanthane
7	C ₂₅ -Cheilanthane 17R+17S
8	C ₂₄ -Tetracyclic terpane
9	C ₂₆ -Cheilanthane 17R+17S
10	C ₂₈ -Cheilanthane 17R+17S
11	C ₂₉ -Cheilanthane 17R+17S
12	18 α (H)-22,29,30-Trisnorneohopane
13	17 α (H)-22,29,30-Trisnorhopane
14	28,30-Bisnorhopane
15	17 α (H),21 β (H)-30-Norhopane
16	18 α (H)-30-Norneohopane
17	Diahopane
18	Oleanane
19	17 α (H),21 β (H)-Hopane
20	17 α (H),21 β (H)-29-Homohopane 22S+22R
21	17 α (H),21 β (H)-29-Bishomohopane 22S+22R
22	17 α (H),21 β (H)-29-Trishomohopane 22S+22R
23	17 α (H),21 β (H)-29-Tetrahomohopane 22S+22R
24	17 α (H),21 β (H)-29-Pentahomohopane 22S+22R

Table 1: Lithological description, stratigraphic heights, TOC values in wt.%, and Rock Eval/TOC data of samples. Original carbon organic values (TOC_o) were calculated according to Baskin (1997) and Jarvie et al. (1997).

Sample	Section	Lithological description	Height	TOC	TOC _o	S2	S3	HI	
CH13	Chitamena River	Dark grey shale	324.5	0.85	0.91	2.65	0.28	312,54	
CH12		I'	Dark grey shale alternating with sand-size siliceous beds	262.0	0.89	1.00	2.51	0.26	282,02
CH11			Dark grey mudstone	247.0	0.88	0.89	3.68	0.41	398,18
CH10		II'	Dark grey shale	224.4	0.75	0.83	1.81	0.19	241,33
CH9			Dark grey shale	219.9	0.82	0.90	2.41	0.27	293,90
CH8		III'	Dark grey shale alternating with white silt-size layers	152.4	1.24	1.26	4.76	0.48	383,87
CH7			Dark grey shale alternating with sand-size siliceous beds	151.0	0.75	0.85	1.99	0.23	264,00
CH6		III'	Grey shale alternating with thin siliceous layers	88.5	0.80	0.99	1.45	0.18	181,87
CH5			Grey shale slightly silt-sized grained	63.3	0.65	0.79	1.19	0.13	182,29
CH4			Grey shale alternating with grey mudstone layers	43.5	0.69	0.83	1.38	0.15	199,90
CH3			Grey shale	17.0	1.04	1.27	1.93	0.23	183,80
CH2			Dark grey mudstone	12.7	2.49	2.90	3.04	0.62	122,08
CH1			Grey siliceous mudstone	0.3	1.09	1.32	1.05	0.27	103,95
G10			Guaguaquí River-s1	Black shale	360.0	6.46	9,37	9.99	0.22
G9	Post-OEA2	Black shale		336.0	4.71	6,96	6.94	0.45	148,27
G8		Black calcareous shale alternating with limestone layers		297.5	5.23	7,48	7.40	0.19	181,31
G7		Black calcareous siltstone with calcite veins		268.8	5.48	8,00	7.52	0.61	156,75
G6	OEA2	Black calcareous shale		151.0	3.35	4,93	5.44	0.34	162,19
G5		Black calcareous shale		144.5	5.51	7,94	9.41	0.37	170,78
G4	Pre-OEA2	Black shale with presence of hydrocarbons		120.5	3.21	4,75	8.14	0.33	158,91
G3		Black calcareous shale		81.0	1.84	2,78	2.72	0.21	147,47
G2		Dark grey calcareous mudstone		20.0	2.11	3,19	3.08	0.22	145,97
G1		Dark grey calcareous shale-slightly silt-grained		6.3	2.81	4,20	4.44	0.18	151,76
G3bis		-s2		Black calcareous siltstone	60.0	1.91	3,27	1.29	0.20
G2bis	Dark grey shale with limestone levels			44.8	8.27	13,28	6.74	0.69	81,49
G1bis	Black calcareous shale			2.8	8.18	13,10	7.04	0.33	86,00
G4tris	-s3	Dark grey laminated calcareous shale to siltstone		148.3	2.92	5,05	1.33	0.20	45,54
G3tris		Dark grey laminated calcareous shale to siltstone	93.2	10.89	17,77	3.02	2.63	27,73	
G2tris		Dark grey laminated calcareous shale to siltstone	78.3	6.66	11,30	1.72	1.62	25,82	
G1tris		Dark grey laminated calcareous shale	12.0	9.57	15,85	2.17	0.17	22,67	
G6tetrtris	-s4	Black calcareous mudstone	567.3	2.65	4,49	1.93	0.15	72,83	
G5tetrtris		Black calcareous mudstone	458.2	3.62	6,07	2.72	1.21	75,13	
G4tetrtris		Black shale with carbonate veins and pyrite ammonites	352.2	1.93	3,32	1.21	0.11	62,69	
G3tetrtris		Black mudstone with carbonate veins	297.3	2.41	4,07	1.89	0.14	78,42	
G2tetrtris		Black calcareous laminated siltstone with shaly levels	234.0	6.00	9,57	6.78	0.19	113,00	
G1tetrtris		Black calcareous shale with pale limestone levels	32.2	2.21	3,74	1.76	0.15	79,63	
H303		Hatalaguna River	Grey to blackish mudstone	415.2	0.84	1.22	0.25	0.37	29,76
H291	Bioturbated grey mudstone		403.2	2.78	4,09	0.07	0.40	2,50	
H285	Bioturbated grey discontinuously-laminated mudstone		397.2	3.32	4,87	0.11	0.35	3,31	
H282	Grey discontinuously-laminated siltstone/mudstone		394.0	1.74	2,44	0.95	0.07	54,59	
H228	Grey mudstone with levels of pale limestone		319.0	1.28	1,86	0.40	0.12	31,25	
H161	Grey mudstone with levels of grey limestone		233.1	0.82	1,15	0.41	0.10	50,00	
H86	Black shale		121.2	1.47	2,14	0.39	0.28	26,53	
H72	Black shale with intercalation of silt/sand-size levels		107.2	1.67	2,42	0.53	0.49	31,73	
H56	Black shale		91.0	1.70	2,46	0.52	0.43	30,58	
H29	Black shale with alternance of sand-size levels		64.3	1.71	2,51	0.25	0.56	14,61	
H10	Black mudstone		45.0	1.34	1,98	0.10	0.44	7,46	
H8	Black mudstone		8.0	1.01	1,50	0.08	0.55	8,55	
M2	Minero River		Black shale	278.0	2.04	3,67	0.05	0.11	3,37
M1			Black mudstone	77.3	1.73	3,13	0.04	0.75	2,31
Z4bis	Upper Reserve	Grey siliceous laminated limestone	48.0	1.32	2,36	0.32	0.68	24,24	
Z3bis		Black calcareous siltstone	29.2	1.92	3,07	1.93	0.16	100,52	
Z2bis		Black calcareous mudstone/siltstone	6.3	1.67	2,63	1.98	0.16	121,58	
Z1bis		Black calcareous mudstone/siltstone	2.3	2.01	3,25	1.90	0.36	94,51	

Sample	Section	Lithological description	Height	TOC	TOC ₀	S2	S3	HI
Z6	Lower La Zambra Reserve	Black siliceous mudstone	105.5	1.87	3.36	0.18	1.06	9.62
Z5		Black siliceous mudstone/siltstone	83.3	2.12	3.65	1.09	0.44	51.41
Z4		Dark grey laminated limestone	79.8	1.08	1.96	0.10	0.60	9.25
Z3		Black siliceous mudstone	73.5	2.88	5.15	0.14	1.67	4.86
Z2		Black laminated siliceous mudstone/siltstone	63.8	5.09	8.71	1.69	1.91	33.54
Z1		Black laminated siliceous mudstone	16.3	5.92	10.19	0.94	2.73	15.88
WL5	West Lengupá River	Black discontinuously-wavy-laminated shale	226.6	8.92	11.29	2.03	0.16	22.75
WL4		Black discontinuously-wavy-laminated siltstone	217.5	4.11	5.24	1.48	0.11	36.01
WL3		Black discontinuously-wavy-laminated shale/siltstone	213.0	1.34	1.74	0.37	0.10	27.61
WL2		Black discontinuously-wavy-laminated shale	93.0	1.24	1.61	0.31	0.12	25.00
WL1		Black discontinuously-wavy-laminated shale/siltstone	27.0	2.62	3.41	0.47	0.09	17.93
EL5	East Lengupá River	Slightly metamorphised black coaly shale	367.5	1.49	1.77	0.13	0.36	8.72
EL4		Black shale with alternation of sandstone layers	331.9	1.91	2.26	0.24	0.12	12.56
EL3		Slightly metamorphised black coaly shale	300.5	15.54	17.89	1.07	0.49	6.88
EL2		Slightly metamorphised black shale	238.5	4.18	4.92	0.47	1.40	11.24
EL1		Slightly metamorphised black coaly shale	13.9	24.31	27.44	1.91	0.25	7.85

Notes: Stratigraphic heights expressed in meters above the base of each (sub)-section. S2 in mg HC/g rock, while S3 in mg CO₂/g rock; and HI in mg HC/g TOC.

Table 2: Bitumen yields (EOM), $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ data (‰), measured and Tmax-based calculated vitrinite reflectances (%), as well as maturity-related molecular parameters for the saturate and aromatic fractions in the study rocks

Sample	%22S	%20S	% $\beta\beta$	MPI-1	Rc1	MAI	MDI	Rc2	VR	EOM	Tmax	Ro calc	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$
CH13	51	38	25	0.78	0.87	--	--	--	--	--	430	0.58	-27.25
CH12	50	39	24	0.81	0.88	--	--	--	0.58	3.33	431	0.60	-27.66
CH11	50	38	24	0.73	0.84	--	--	--	--	4.83	427	0.53	-28.09
CH10	52	--	26	0.62	0.77	--	--	--	0.57	5.00	431	0.60	-27.49
CH9	54	--	28	0.56	0.74	--	--	--	--	0.67	431	0.60	-27.46
CH8	56	38	--	0.75	0.85	--	--	--	0.58	4.83	428	0.54	-25.90
CH7	55	39	30	0.61	0.77	--	--	--	--	3.66	432	0.61	-26.30
CH6	59	43	--	--	--	--	--	--	0.62	2.16	435	0.67	-25.72
CH5	57	41	31	0.61	0.77	--	--	--	--	3.83	437	0.70	-26.75
CH4	60	41	33	--	--	--	--	--	--	3.33	436	0.69	-26.75
CH3	58	42	34	0.68	0.81	--	--	--	0.61	5.67	438	0.72	-25.76
CH2	62	41	32	0.73	0.84	--	--	--	0.61	2.67	439	0.74	-24.62
CH1	59	42	33	0.57	0.75	--	--	--	0.61	1.16	437	0.71	-24.24
G10	--	--	--	0.99	1.00	--	--	--	--	--	462	1.16	--
G9	--	--	--	0.98	0.99	--	--	--	0.92	--	460	1.12	-28.15
G8	--	--	--	0.99	1.00	--	--	--	0.98	36.83	463	1.17	-28.09
G7	58	52	67	0.91	0.94	--	--	--	--	31.67	452	0.97	-27.58
G6	--	55	66	0.86	0.91	--	--	--	--	--	455	1.03	-23.25
G5	--	55	65	0.85	0.91	--	--	--	0.95	36.50	455	1.03	-23.74
G4	--	53	66	0.86	0.91	--	--	--	--	38.50	455	1.03	-26.70
G3	59	55	71	--	--	--	--	--	--	9.50	447	0.89	-26.33
G2	57	54	70	--	--	--	--	--	0.91	14.17	445	0.85	-26.37
G1	57	55	70	0.87	0.92	--	--	--	0.92	37.50	448	0.90	-26.41
G3bis	--	--	--	1.21	1.12	0.55	0.29	1.15	1.40	4.33	464	1.19	-27.46
G2bis	--	--	--	--	--	0.57	0.29	1.15	1.36	7.17	475	1.39	-27.15
G1bis	--	--	--	1.09	1.05	0.56	0.28	1.13	1.25	35.67	471	1.31	-27.84
G4tris	--	--	--	1.35	1.49	0.70	0.48	1.61	--	0.33	498	1.80	-27.02
G3tris	--	--	--	--	--	0.76	0.45	1.53	1.61	1.50	511	--	-27.62
G2tris	--	--	--	1.34	1.50	0.69	0.44	1.53	1.80	1.17	573	--	-27.56
G1tris	--	--	--	1.31	1.52	0.74	0.46	1.57	1.70	1.67	577	--	-26.85
G6tetris	--	--	--	1.33	1.19	0.50	0.30	1.18	1.36	7.17	469	1.28	-25.51
G5tetris	--	--	--	1.23	1.14	0.65	0.28	1.12	--	10.50	468	1.28	-27.27
G4tetris	--	--	--	1.31	1.18	0.57	0.32	1.22	--	5.83	470	1.30	-26.82
G3tetris	--	--	--	1.31	1.18	0.52	0.30	1.18	1.29	7.50	470	1.30	-26.66
G2tetris	--	--	--	1.26	1.16	0.58	0.29	1.15	1.20	12.17	471	1.32	-27.38
G1tetris	--	--	--	1.30	1.18	0.56	0.30	1.18	--	8.01	475	1.39	-26.53
H303	62	--	--	--	--	0.59	0.35	1.29	--	7.00	454	1.00	-26.16
H291	57	53	67	--	--	0.62	0.28	1.13	0.97	≤ 0.15	484	--	-25.64
H285	--	--	--	--	--	0.61	0.28	1.13	0.97	0.33	453	0.99	-25.47
H282	--	--	--	1.19	1.12	0.49	0.29	1.15	--	15.66	455	1.03	-25.42
H228	--	--	--	1.35	1.21	0.49	0.29	1.15	--	8.17	460	1.12	-25.88
H161	--	--	--	1.30	1.18	0.55	0.31	1.20	0.92	9.33	464	1.19	-25.81

Sample	%22S	%20S	%ββ	MPI-1	Rc ₁	MAI	MDI	Rc ₂	VR	EOM	T _{max}	Ro calc	δ ¹³ C
H86	--	--	--	--	--	0.55	0.30	1.17	--	3.83	468	1.26	-26.08
H72	57	52	69	--	--	0.58	0.33	1.25	0.94	3.16	466	1.22	-25.47
H56	--	--	--	--	--	0.58	0.34	1.27	--	4.00	458	1.08	-25.26
H29	--	--	--	--	--	0.65	0.30	1.17	0.97	0.83	459	1.10	-25.01
H10	--	55	70	--	--	0.61	0.34	1.22	0.99	0.67	459	1.10	-25.09
H8	--	55	69	--	--	0.62	0.31	1.20	--	--	502	--	--
Z4bis	61	53	71	--	--	0.48	0.30	1.16	1.07	1.17	459	1.10	-26.57
Z3bis	--	--	--	1.18	1.11	0.49	0.28	1.11	--	13.33	468	1.26	-26.62
Z2bis	--	--	--	--	--	0.48	0.29	1.12	--	6.50	465	1.21	-26.22
Z1bis	--	--	--	1.21	1.12	0.52	0.29	1.12	1.09	16.33	458	1.08	-26.48
Z6	--	--	--	--	--	0.55	0.30	1.16	--	--	466	1.23	--
Z5	--	--	--	--	--	0.55	0.30	1.16	1.01	0.50	463	1.17	-26.11
Z4	62	--	--	--	--	0.61	--	--	--	0.17	460	1.12	-25.93
Z3	61	54	68	--	--	0.60	0.30	1.16	--	2.17	461	1.14	-25.33
Z2	--	--	--	--	--	0.50	0.31	1.17	1.04	2.00	459	1.10	-25.29
Z1	--	--	--	--	--	0.50	0.28	1.11	1.10	1.83	465	1.21	-25.23
WL5	--	--	--	0.73	1.86	0.78	0.54	1.76	--	0.50	520	--	-22.71
WL4	--	--	--	0.71	1.87	0.80	0.51	1.69	--	0.83	505	--	-22.48
WL3	--	--	--	0.90	1.76	0.81	0.50	1.67	1.84	1.16	549	--	-22.66
WL2	--	--	--	0.86	1.78	0.88	0.55	1.79	1.69	≤ 0.15	534	--	-23.95
WL1	--	--	--	0.79	1.82	0.82	0.57	1.83	--	0.33	551	--	-22.99
EL5	--	--	--	0.70	1.88	0.89	0.63	1.98	--	≤ 0.15	603	--	-24.50
EL4	--	--	--	0.69	1.89	0.86	0.62	1.96	--	≤ 0.15	599	--	-24.22
EL3	--	--	--	0.72	1.87	0.90	0.59	1.89	1.88	≤ 0.15	603	--	-23.76
EL2	--	--	--	0.73	1.86	0.92	0.60	1.91	--	≤ 0.15	598	--	-23.24
EL1	--	--	--	0.71	1.87	0.90	0.58	1.86	1.74	≤ 0.15	596	--	-23.59
M2	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2.07	≤ 0.15	492	--	-21.05
M1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	2.03	≤ 0.15	493	--	-21.22
Une	60	55	70	0.85	0.91	--	--	--	--	--	449	0.92	-24.90
Guadalupe	59	38	28	0.33	0.60	--	--	--	--	--	432	0.62	-23.96

Notes: VR=measured vitrinite reflectance; bitumen yield in mg HC/g rock; %22S=17α,21β(H)-29-bishomohopane 22S and 22R ratio (%); %20S=5α,14α,17α(H)-stigmastane 20S and 20R ratio (%); %ββ=ratio (%) of C₂₉ isosteranes to C₂₉ regular steranes; MPI-1=1.5·(2-MP+3-MP)/(P+1-MP+9-MP), %Rc₁=0.4+0.6·MPI-1 (values < 1.35%) and Rc₁=2.3-0.6·MPI-1 (values ranging between 1.35 and 2.0%); MAI=1-MA/(1-MA+2-MA); MDI=4-MD/(1-MD+3-MD+4-MD), assuming maturity values from 1.0 to 2.0%; %Rc₂=0.434+2.464·MDI; δ¹³C values (‰); T_{max} in °C; and %Ro calc = 0.018·T_{max} - 7.16, assuming % Ro calc from 420 to 500°C and S₂ ≥ 0.1 (Jarvie et al., 2001).

Table 3: Molecular parameters, sulphur content (%), and V/Ni ratio as geochemical indicators of depositional paleo-environment, lithology and source for saturate and aromatic fractions in the samples. DMDI-1 and EAI expressed in percentage.

Sample	Pr/Ph	V/Ni	Flu3	St	DMDI-1	EAI	DMA/TMA	26/25T	22/21T	24/23T	29/30H	DBT/P	Dia/ST	31R/30H
CH13	2.55	0.34	0.43	0.19	72	--	--	1.06	0.22	0.69	0.65	0.15	0.35	0.27
CH12	2.89	0.32	0.45	0.20	73	--	--	1.07	0.23	0.68	0.66	0.15	0.35	0.26
CH11	1.91	0.38	0.31	0.18	72	81	0.81	1.02	0.16	0.62	0.57	0.14	0.36	0.27
CH10	1.95	0.30	0.43	0.16	71	--	--	1.15	0.18	0.70	0.56	0.15	0.43	0.24
CH9	2.65	0.33	0.29	0.17	69	82	0.80	1.08	0.21	0.69	0.61	0.07	0.36	0.30
CH8	2.30	0.38	0.31	0.18	71	--	--	1.11	0.17	0.65	0.53	--	0.38	0.28
CH7	2.38	0.36	0.41	0.15	70	77	0.85	1.08	0.21	0.63	0.63	0.10	0.38	0.25
CH6	2.86	--	--	0.18	73	80	0.83	1.00	0.18	0.71	0.62	0.06	0.40	0.29
CH5	3.01	0.39	0.42	0.19	73	79	0.78	1.05	0.23	0.62	0.52	0.10	0.44	0.28
CH4	2.39	--	0.28	0.17	70	--	--	1.13	0.20	0.67	0.62	0.09	0.41	0.24
CH3	2.99	0.37	0.29	0.20	73	83	0.76	1.10	0.17	0.72	0.64	0.07	0.36	0.26
CH2	2.11	0.29	0.28	0.16	72	82	0.74	1.11	0.18	0.61	0.55	0.06	0.40	0.25
CH1	3.02	0.35	0.30	0.17	76	80	0.73	1.02	0.19	0.66	0.64	0.10	0.39	0.30
G10	0.99	1.17	--	0.33	63	70	1.30	0.97	0.26	1.09	--	0.40	0.36	--
G9	0.98	1.16	--	0.33	64	71	1.29	0.96	0.27	1.07	--	0.41	0.35	--
G8	0.98	1.19	--	0.34	63	69	1.28	0.95	0.28	1.05	--	0.42	0.36	--
G7	1.00	1.14	0.13	0.26	67	73	1.21	0.85	0.24	1.11	0.61	0.27	0.32	0.27
G6	0.96	2.82	0.12	0.36	65	69	1.20	0.91	0.28	1.15	--	0.22	0.27	--
G5	0.94	2.90	0.12	0.38	66	68	1.25	0.90	0.26	1.14	--	0.23	0.25	--
G4	0.99	2.95	0.13	0.35	64	71	1.13	0.92	0.30	1.17	--	0.20	0.30	--
G3	1.02	--	0.18	0.19	62	72	0.98	0.92	0.25	1.02	0.56	--	0.34	0.25
G2	1.09	--	0.19	0.26	65	70	1.01	0.97	0.22	0.93	0.60	--	0.30	0.26
G1	1.06	1.07	0.18	0.27	--	--	1.42	0.96	0.24	0.99	0.63	0.17	0.29	0.29
G3bis	--	1.24	0.19	0.26	66	69	1.14	--	--	--	--	0.20	--	--

Sample	Pr/Ph	V/Ni	Flu3	St	DMDI-1	EAI	DMA/TMA	26/25T	22/21T	24/23T	29/30H	DBT/P	Dia/ST	31R/30H
G2bis	--	--	--	0.33	65	--	0.98	--	--	--	--	0.44	--	--
G1bis	--	1.29	0.16	0.27	67	70	1.12	--	--	--	--	0.19	--	--
G4tris	--	1.25	0.19	0.28	--	--	1.25	--	--	--	--	0.30	--	--
G3tris	--	--	--	0.26	--	--	0.88	--	--	--	--	0.34	--	--
G2tris	--	1.69	0.15	0.27	--	--	1.14	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
G1tris	--	1.60	0.16	0.28	--	--	1.01	--	--	--	--	0.30	--	--
G6tetris	--	1.33	0.14	0.27	65	69	0.86	--	--	--	--	0.13	--	--
G5tetris	--	1.31	0.16	0.26	63	71	1.05	--	--	--	--	0.14	--	--
G4tetris	--	1.35	0.18	0.29	66	70	1.13	--	--	--	--	0.12	--	--
G3tetris	--	1.28	0.18	0.27	64	70	0.93	--	--	--	--	0.12	--	--
G2tetris	--	1.30	0.16	0.28	67	69	1.15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
G1tetris	--	1.29	0.12	0.31	65	72	0.88	--	--	--	--	0.23	--	--
H303	--	--	0.30	0.17	75	--	0.72	--	--	--	--	0.02	--	--
H291	--	0.65	--	0.16	69	79	--	--	--	--	--	0.03	--	--
H285	--	0.63	0.29	0.19	73	80	--	--	--	--	--	0.02	--	--
H282	--	0.61	--	0.18	--	79	0.76	--	--	--	--	0.05	--	--
H228	--	0.70	0.38	0.23	73	75	0.79	--	--	--	--	0.09	--	--
H161	--	0.69	0.43	0.22	77	78	0.83	--	--	--	--	0.09	--	--
H86	--	--	0.41	0.17	72	81	0.80	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
H72	--	--	0.30	0.18	76	80	--	--	--	--	--	0.02	--	--
H56	--	--	--	0.16	72	76	0.81	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
H29	--	--	0.30	0.17	71	82	0.83	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
H10	--	--	0.27	0.15	76	--	0.73	--	--	--	--	0.01	--	--
H8	--	--	0.27	0.16	75	--	0.75	--	--	--	--	0.01	--	--
Z4bis	--	1.20	0.21	0.32	67	69	1.24	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Sample	Pr/Ph	V/Ni	Flu3	St	DMDI-1	EAI	DMA/TMA	26/25T	22/21T	24/23T	29/30H	DBT/P	Dia/ST	31R/30H
Z3bis	--	1.08	0.22	0.28	--	72	1.14	--	--	--	--	0.03	--	--
Z2bis	--	1.10	--	0.26	65	68	--	--	--	--	--	0.01	--	--
Z1bis	--	1.09	0.20	0.27	65	71	0.95	--	--	--	--	0.02	--	--
Z6	--	1.07	0.21	0.20	--	--	0.90	--	--	--	--	0.01	--	--
Z5	--	1.06	0.21	0.19	--	--	0.89	--	--	--	--	0.01	--	--
Z4	--	1.18	0.22	0.23	66	70	--	--	--	--	--	0.09	--	--
Z3	--	--	0.20	0.18	63	70	--	--	--	--	--	0.01	--	--
Z2	--	--	0.19	0.20	64	69	0.86	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Z1	--	--	0.21	0.19	65	--	1.31	--	--	--	--	0.01	--	--
M2	--	2.34	0.24	0.20	--	--	1.10	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
M1	--	2.41	0.16	0.19	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	0.41	--	--
WL5	--	0.14	0.75	0.12	--	--	0.69	--	--	--	--	0.04	--	--
WL4	--	0.13	0.68	0.13	--	--	0.68	--	--	--	--	0.05	--	--
WL3	--	0.13	0.63	0.12	--	--	0.67	--	--	--	--	0.07	--	--
WL2	--	--	--	0.13	--	--	0.68	--	--	--	--	0.06	--	--
WL1	--	0.12	0.61	0.14	--	--	0.66	--	--	--	--	0.06	--	--
EL5	--	--	--	0.10	--	--	0.61	--	--	--	--	0.15	--	--
EL4	--	0.10	0.88	0.09	--	--	0.60	--	--	--	--	0.14	--	--
EL3	--	0.11	0.77	0.08	--	--	0.61	--	--	--	--	0.12	--	--
EL2	--	0.11	0.90	0.10	--	--	0.59	--	--	--	--	0.10	--	--
EL1	--	0.10	0.93	0.09	--	--	0.62	--	--	--	--	0.02	--	--
Une	3.15	0.12	--	0.20	--	--	--	1.19	--	1.16	0.54	0.09	0.51	0.21
Guadalupe	3.76	0.10	--	0.09	--	--	--	1.15	--	1.17	0.50	--	0.50	0.23

Notes: Dia/ST=diasterane ratio; DBT/P=dibenzothiophene/phenanthrene; 22/21T=C₂₂/C₂₁-cheillanthane; Pr/Ph=pritanes/phytanes; St=sulphur content; DMA=1,2+1,3+cis/trans-1,4-DMA; TMA=1,3,5+1,3,6+cis/trans-1,3,4-TMA; 29/30H=30-norhopane/C₃₀-hopane; DMDI-1=3,4-DMD/(3,4+4,9-DMD); 24/23T=C₂₄-tricyclic terpane/C₂₃-tricyclic terpane; 26/25T=ratio of C₂₆-tricyclic terpanes between C₂₅-tricyclic terpanes; EAI=2-EA/(2+1-EA); Flu3=three-fluorenes ratio; and 31R/30H=29-homohopane 22R/C₃₀-hopane.

CRedit author statement

Erika Lorenzo: Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Investigation, Validation, Supervision; **Antonio Morato:** Formal analysis, Visualization, Investigation, Resources
Karla Quintero: Writing - Review & Editing, Data curation.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: